

AUTOREGRESSIVE SPECTRAL MODELING OF MOTOR UNIT ACTION POTENTIALS

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ABSTRACT

Quantitative electromyographic (EMG) signal analysis in the time domain for motor unit action potential (MUAP) classification and disease identification has been well documented over the last years. Considerable work has also been carried out in the frequency domain using classical power spectrum techniques. Although MUAP autoregressive (AR) spectral analysis was suggested as a diagnostic tool by a number of studies, it has not been thoroughly investigated yet. This work investigates the application of AR modeling in the analysis of MUAPs recorded from normal (NOR) subjects and patients suffering with Motor Neuron Disease (MND) and myopathy (MYO). The optimum AR model order was determined using the Akaike information criterion (AIC), and the AR coefficients were identified by the modified covariance method. The following MUAP feature sets were calculated: i) time domain measures, ii) AR spectral measures, iii) AR coefficients and model order, and iv) cepstral coefficients. Two different feature selection methods were used: i) the univariate analysis and ii) the multiple covariance analysis. Both methods showed that: i) the duration measure is the best discriminative feature among the time parameters and ii) the median frequency is the best discriminator among the frequency measures. Furthermore, the recognition rate of the above feature sets was investigated using the K-means nearest neighbour cluster analysis and the Euclidean distance classifier for three classes, NOR, MND, and MYO. For the K-means cluster analysis, results showed that the highest diagnostic yield was obtained with the time domain measures, followed by the cepstral coefficients, the AR spectral parameters, and the AR coefficients. For the Euclidean distance classifier, the highest diagnostic yield was obtained again with the time domain measures, followed by the AR spectral measures, the cepstral coefficients, and the AR coefficients. In conclusion, MUAP AR modeling spectral analysis, combined with time domain analysis provide useful information in the diagnosis of myopathology.

To my family

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

α	Level of significance
α_k	Autoregressive coefficient at time index k
$\alpha_p(k)$	Autoregressive coefficient of order p at time index k
$\alpha_p^b(m)$	Backward linear prediction coefficient of order p at time index m
$\alpha_p^f(m)$	Forward linear prediction coefficient of order p at time index m
$\alpha_p^{fb}(m)$	Forward and backward linear prediction coefficient of order p at time index m
$\underline{\alpha}_p^{fb}$	Vector of p forward and backward linear prediction coefficients
A	Total number of reverse arrangements
Amp	Amplitude
ACS	Autocorrelation sequence
AIC	Akaike information criterion
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
ANN	Artificial neural network
AR	Autoregressive
ARMA	Autoregressive moving average
A/D	Analogue to digital
BW	Bandwidth
BWE	Equivalent bandwidth
c_n	Cepstral coefficient at time index n
c_{n_c}	Complex cepstrum
c_{n_r}	Real cepstrum
$C(f)$	Normalized cumulative residuals periodogram
CF	Centre frequency

CAT	Criterion autoregressive transfer function
<i>DFT</i>	Discrete Fourier transform
Dur	Duration
$\bar{\hat{e}}$	Mean value of residual error estimate
$\hat{e}(n)$	Discrete time residual error estimate
$e_p^b(n)$	Backward linear prediction error of order p at time index n
$e_p^f(n)$	Forward linear prediction error of order p at time index n
e_{NORM}	Normalized residual energy
ED	Euclidean distance
EMG	Electromyography
f	Frequency
F_0	Peak power frequency
F_1	Lower cut-off frequency
F_2	Upper cut-off frequency
F_5	Frequency at -5dB
F_{10}	Frequency at -10dB
F_{15}	Frequency at -15dB
F_{20}	Frequency at -20dB
F_{25}	Frequency at -25dB
<i>FMED</i>	Median frequency
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
FPE	Final prediction error
<i>IDFT</i>	Inverse discrete Fourier transform
$k_p = \alpha_p(p)$	Reflection coefficient of order p
K	Number of clusters
max	Maximum
min	Minimum

mn	Mean
M_0	Moment of order zero
M_1	Moment of order one
M_2	Moment of order two
MA	Moving average
MDL	Minimum description length
ME	Maximum Entropy
MLE	Maximum likelihood estimation
MND	Motor Neuron Disease
MUAP	Motor unit action potential
MYO	Myopathy
M-Covar	Multiple covariance
n	Discrete time index
N	Number of data samples
N_k	Number of subjects in class k
N_s	Number of samples in each segment
N_{seg}	Number of segments
N_t	Total number of subjects
NPV	Negative predictive value
NOR	Normal
p	Autoregressive model order
$P_e(f)$	Residuals spectral density
P_{max}	Maximum power
$P_{ww}(f)$	Power spectral density of white noise sequence $w(n)$
$P_{xx}(f)$	Power spectral density
$P_{AR}(f)$	Autoregressive power spectral density
$P_{NORM}(f)$	Normalized power spectral density
P_{100}	Power at 100Hz

P_{200}	Power at 200Hz
P_{300}	Power at 300Hz
P_{500}	Power at 500Hz
P_{750}	Power at 750Hz
P_{1000}	Power at 1000Hz
P_{1250}	Power at 1250Hz
P_{1500}	Power at 1500Hz
P_{2000}	Power at 2000Hz
P_{2500}	Power at 2500Hz
PPV	Positive predictive value
Ph	Phases
PC	Personal computer
PPR	Parametric pattern recognition
PSD	Power spectral density
q	Quantization step
Q	Quality factor
Q	Portmanteau test statistic
Q_1	Lower quartile
Q_3	Upper quartile
r	Run
$r_p(m, j)$	Autocorrelation sequence of order p at time difference indices m and j
$\underline{r}_p(m, j)$	Vector of p autocorrelation sequences at time difference indices m and j
$r_{ww}(n)$	Autocorrelation of white noise sequence $w(n)$
$\underline{R}_p$	Autocorrelation matrix of order p
RLS	Recursive least square
s	Sample standard deviation
s^2	Sample variance
SE	Sensitivity

<i>SP</i>	Specificity
<i>SpArea</i>	Spike area
<i>SpDur</i>	Spike duration
<i>SEMG</i>	Surface electromyography
<i>SIQR</i>	Semi-interquartile range
<i>T</i>	Sampling period
<i>TN</i>	True negative
<i>TP</i>	True positive
<i>T</i>	Turns
<i>U</i>	Window energy
<i>Univar</i>	Univariate
$w(n)$	Discrete time white noise sequence
$W(f)$	Discrete Fourier transform of white noise sequence $w(n)$
$\bar{x}$	Sample mean value of x
$x(n)$	Discrete time function
$\hat{x}(n)$	An estimate of discrete time function $x(n)$
$\hat{x}^b(n)$	Backward linear prediction estimate at time index n
$\hat{x}^f(n)$	Forward linear prediction estimate at time index n
$x_\omega(n)$	Discrete time windowed function
X	Random variable
$X(f)$	Discrete Fourier transform of discrete time function $x(n)$
z	Complex variable
∂	Partial derivative operator
ν	Degrees of freedom
ρ_p^{fb}	Forward and backward linear prediction squared error of order p
ρ_{xy}	Sample correlation of variables x and y
$\hat{\rho}_p$	Linear prediction error variance estimate of order p

$\hat{\rho}_w$	An estimate of the white noise sequence variance
χ^2	Statistical chi-square variable
$\omega(n)$	Discrete time window function
$\mathbf{0}_p$	Vector of p zero elements
% CCs	Percentage of correct classifications
% FPS	Percentage of false positives
% FNS	Percentage of false negatives

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Electromyography (EMG) is the study of the electrical activity of muscle, and forms a valuable aid in the diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders. The main characteristic of these disorders is that they cause muscular weakness and/or wasting. EMG findings are used to detect and describe different disease processes affecting the motor unit, the smallest functional unit of the muscle. At slight voluntary muscle contraction the motor unit action potential (MUAP) is recorded, that reflects the electrical activity of a single anatomical motor unit. At the early days of electromyography, neurophysiologists used to assess MUAPs from their shape by watching the oscilloscope and their audio characteristics. With these simple means, it was possible for an experienced electrophysiologist to detect abnormalities with reasonable accuracy. However, MUAP assessment although satisfactory for the detection of obvious abnormalities was not adequate for less apparent deviations or mixed patterns of abnormalities. These ambiguous cases called for quantitative MUAP analysis (Buchthal and Kamieniecka, 1982). Buchthal and coworkers introduced manual methods for quantitative MUAP analysis in the fifties (Buchthal et al, 1954a,b; Buchthal, 1957). MUAPs recorded photographically were selected for analysis. Manual measurement of duration, amplitude, and number of phases was carried out. Twenty potentials were collected, and their data was then compared to values obtained from the corresponding muscle in age-matched normal subjects. Manual methods although important at the time were time consuming and liable to variable sources of error due to the subjective measurement of the MUAP parameters of interest.

The advent of computer technology in the last twenty years allowed scientists to renew their efforts so as to improve the diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders. Computer aided EMG processing saves time, standardizes the measurements, and enables the extraction of features which cannot be calculated manually. Automated EMG analysis has been carried out both in the time domain and in the frequency domain. Time domain techniques that rely on extracting features for classification directly from the waveform, such as MUAP duration, are somewhat difficult to measure automatically and their manual measurement depends on one's intuition. Signal analysis in the frequency domain reveals the frequency characteristics of the signals and may offer an alternative tool. However, the Fourier transform power spectrum estimates suffer from reduced frequency resolution and spectral leakage effects. Spectral analysis of signals by autoregressive (AR) modeling is a better power spectral density estimation method, characterized by higher resolution and avoiding spectral leakage effects (Marple, 1987).

In clinical EMG, AR MUAP analysis was suggested as a diagnostic tool by Coatrieux (1983), Maranzana et al (1984), and Basmajian et al (1985) but not as yet thoroughly investigated. The work carried out in this paper aims at investigating the application of AR modeling in MUAP analysis. Furthermore, feature selection analysis was performed to identify features with the highest discriminative power. The classification performance of various selected features was also examined.

1.1 Original Aspects of the Work

The first original contribution of this work is the application of AR modeling on MUAPs recorded from normal (NOR) subjects as well as from subjects suffering with Motor Neurone Disease (MND) and myopathy (MYO). Features extracted were grouped as follows: i) AR spectral measures, ii) AR coefficients and model order, and iii) cepstral coefficients. The above feature sets are also compared to time domain features.

Furthermore, the discriminative power of the above mentioned feature sets is evaluated. Feature selection analysis was carried out using the univariate and the multivariate analysis methods. The classification score of selected features was also investigated using the K-means nearest neighbour cluster analysis algorithm and the Euclidean distance classifier.

1.2 Guide to Thesis Contents

In Chapter 2 the usefulness of spectral analysis in EMG is discussed. EMG studies using classical and autoregressive spectral estimation analysis methods are briefly reviewed. In AR modeling, EMG studies using both surface and needle electrodes are given. Finally, feature selection studies performed in needle EMG for discriminating various muscle pathologies are presented.

Chapter 3 describes the methodology of AR MUAP analysis employed in this study. This chapter begins with a flowchart outlining the steps required to estimate the AR power spectral density and extract features from the AR model spectral envelope and other measures for classification purposes. Time and frequency analysis of MUAPs are then described in detail. Frequency analysis is carried out using both the fast Fourier transform (FFT) and AR modeling. Various parameters extracted from the AR spectra together with AR and cepstral coefficients are used as diagnostic features. Univariate and multivariate statistical analysis are also presented. Feature selection analysis methods which rank features according to their diagnostic yield are also discussed. Finally, the classification performance of various selected features derived from the AR MUAP analysis and time domain parameters is evaluated using the K-means nearest neighbour algorithm and the Euclidean distance classifier.

In Chapter 4 the results obtained in the AR MUAP analysis are presented. First, the material used in this study is given. The results and findings of the stationarity test, using the run and the reverse arrangement methods, are then given and briefly analysed. The model order selected by the Akaike information criterion (AIC), the final prediction error (FPE), and the minimum description length (MDL) criteria is discussed based on the results of the normalized residual energies. Plots of the Akaike selection criterion function and the linear prediction error variance against model order are also given and their behaviour explained. The fitness of the AR model is checked using the residuals periodogram, the normalized cumulative residuals periodogram, and the portmanteau test statistic. The FFT and AR spectra for three subjects, one from each disease group, are plotted and compared. Group statistics for the MUAP time parameters, for various features extracted from the AR spectra, and for the AR and cepstral coefficients are also tabulated. Differences in their values compared to normal are related to individual muscle pathologies. Univariate and multivariate statistical analysis are also performed on various selected features. Correlation analysis is carried out so as to detect highly correlated features and subsequently exclude them from the feature selection analysis. Feature selection analysis is carried out using the univariate and the multivariate strategies. The ranking of features according to their diagnostic power is presented. Furthermore, the K-means and the Euclidean distance classifiers are used to evaluate the classification performance of selected features. The discriminative ability of selected features is finally investigated and reported.

Discussion of findings in this work is given in Chapter 5. In this chapter, analysis of every step followed in the AR MUAP analysis is given. The method is compared to other methods published in the literature. The ranking of selected features as determined by two different feature selection analysis methods is also given and discussed. At the end of the chapter the classification score of selected features as obtained by the K-means nearest neighbour and the Euclidean distance classifiers is reported.

The last chapter, Chapter 6, summarizes the conclusions of this work, and makes suggestions for further study. Finally, Appendix 1 describes the modified covariance method that computes the AR parameter estimates and from these the AR PSD function.

Chapter 2

SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF EMG SIGNALS

In Chapter 2, the classical and parametric power spectral density estimation techniques are briefly described and compared. The advantages of spectral analysis over time domain analysis are also discussed. Surface and needle EMG studies performed by FFT and AR modeling techniques are briefly reviewed. Finally, feature selection analysis methods for discriminating various muscle diseases in EMG are presented.

2.1 Introduction

Spectral or frequency analysis is the decomposition of a signal into its sinusoidal or complex exponential components. The power spectrum of a signal gives the strength variation of its frequency components. Useful mathematical tools for representing a certain signal in the frequency domain are the Fourier series and the Fourier transform for periodic and aperiodic signals respectively.

The classical power spectral density (PSD) estimation techniques developed using the Fourier transform are the periodogram and the correlogram. The periodogram is considered a direct method because it uses the data sequence directly to compute the PSD. The PSD is actually obtained by taking the squared magnitude of the Fourier transform of the finite data sequence with appropriate statistical averaging. If this averaging is not performed on the finite data sequence then the power spectrum obtained is termed the sample spectrum. The sample spectrum gives a nonstatistically stable spectral estimate. The correlogram, also called an indirect method, computes the autocorrelation sequence from the finite data sequence and in turn its Fourier transform to yield the PSD.

Classical spectral estimation techniques suffer from spectral leakage effects due to the inherent windowing of finite data sets. Both the periodogram and correlogram methods give PSD estimates from a windowed set of data or autocorrelation sequence (ACS) estimates. The periodogram estimate considers the unavailable data zero or periodic with period the number of data samples N . The correlogram estimate assumes the unestimated ACS values zero. Window weighting to alleviate the effect of sidelobes in the frequency domain and the averaging approach to improve the statistical stability of the spectral estimate cause further reduction in the spectral frequency resolution. In the classical PSD estimation method an attempt is made always to produce a

statistically reliable spectral estimate from a finite number of data samples with the highest possible resolution and the minimum sidelobe leakage affects. The drawbacks inherent in the classical PSD estimation methods forced scientists and engineers to focus their attention to the development of alternative power spectrum techniques, like parametric modeling techniques.

Parametric modeling techniques are based on modeling a signal as a linear combination of its past values and the present and past values of a hypothetical input to a system whose output is the given signal. Various parametric models exist, namely autoregressive (AR), moving average (MA), and autoregressive moving average (ARMA) models. Parametric modeling techniques give better PSD estimators, higher spectral resolution, and avoid spectral leakage effects compared to nonparametric or classical spectral estimation techniques (Marple, 1987).

2.2 The usefulness of spectral analysis

The differential diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders from direct (nonparametric) analysis of the EMG signal is complicated by the following: the electrode insertion noise, the signal variations due to the type of muscle effort (weak or strong), the type and size of the motor unit, the number of motor units recruited, and the fact that individual motor unit potentials cannot be clearly distinguished even for weak muscle efforts. Research on parametric models for EMG signals has been carried out extensively in literature. Time domain techniques that rely on extracting features for classification directly from the waveform, such as MUAP duration, are somewhat difficult to measure automatically, and their manual assessment is subjectively evaluated.

On the other hand, power spectrum methods work with single motor unit signals as well as with whole muscle signals. Thus, signals obtained at any level of contraction can be analysed free from inaccurate judgements. This considerably extends the range and scope of the conventional EMG methods. The quantitative nature of the method allows comparisons to be made during the course of disease. It also makes possible the study of the effects of therapy. Another use of the quantitative properties of the method is found in muscle fatigue studies. These investigations would not be feasible with conventional EMG techniques. The spectral analysis makes it possible also to describe the shape of the spectrum in terms of physically well defined parameters. Further, it gives possibilities to relate EMG to physiological events and mechanisms. This ability of the method also applies to surface EMG which finds applications in noninvasive investigations of small children. Finally, spectral analysis reveals properties of the signal which are hidden from visual inspection of the time plot.

2.3 Classical spectral estimation analysis

Experimental applications

The application of classical spectral analysis to EMG signals was implemented

- i) through the use of numerical values of some spectral measures and their comparison with normal values, and
- ii) through parameter identification by using spectral models that fit the experimental data and interpreting spectral findings in terms of physiological parameters describing signal genesis.

Spectral measures

The spectral analysis of EMG signals was originally performed with filter banks in which the signals were split up in frequency components, and their power levels were measured afterwards (Richardson, 1951; Walton, 1952; Kogi and Hakamada, 1962; Kaiser and Petersen, 1962, 1963, 1965). Octave band filters as well as other types of filters were used (Kondo, 1960). Traditional octave band analysers gave power peaks in the EMG spectra ranging from 50-100Hz in case of surface electrodes and 100-200Hz in case of needle electrodes. The rapid development of computers in the 70's displaced filter banks completely. The discrete Fourier transform with the development of fast Fourier transform (FFT) made the analysis of EMG signals much easier and brought results that were previously much more difficult to obtain with.

EMG spectral analysis using pure spectral measures for diagnostic purposes has been carried out extensively over the past forty years. Walton in 1952 confirmed that the power spectrum of myopathies is shifted towards higher frequencies. This was confirmed with the use of the spectrometer which showed frequency peaks displaced to frequencies as high as 400-600Hz. This was also confirmed in a number of other cases (Richardson, 1951; Fex and Krakau, 1957; Gersten et al, 1965; Kopec and Hausmanowa - Petruszewicz, 1966; Carlsson et al, 1972; Sandstedt, 1981).

In the case of neuropathies the power spectrum is displaced towards lower frequencies with the power content in low frequency components being higher as compared with normal spectra (Kaiser and Petersen, 1963, 1965; Gersten et al, 1965; Kopec and Hausmanowa - Petruszewicz, 1966; Herberts et al, 1973; Shigiya et al, 1973; Larsson, 1975; Sandstedt, 1981). Power spectrum analysis of EMG signals using spectral measures as a diagnostic tool found also widespread applications in muscle fatigue studies (Lindstrom and Petersen, 1981).

Parameter identification

The second spectral application is implemented through parameter identification performed by the use of spectral models that fit the experimental data. One type of parameter identification is the determination of the so called dip frequencies from which the propagation velocity of the action potentials can be estimated. Dip analysis was used in muscle fatigue studies. Results showed that spectral changes of the EMG signal during muscle fatigue were caused by a lowering of the propagation velocity (Lindstrom et al, 1970). Later, it was shown that spectral changes were caused by the metabolic alteration of the muscle (Mortimer et al, 1970a). Dip analysis also found application in the description of the EMG development in childhood. Results and discussions on such an investigation are given by Lindstrom et al, 1983.

2.4 Autoregressive spectral estimation analysis in EMG

2.4.1 *Surface EMG*

AR modeling has been usefully applied for the control of prostheses (Graupe and Cline, 1975; Graupe et al, 1978; Sherif et al, 1981; Doerschuk et al, 1983; Triolo et al, 1988; Triolo and Moskowitz, 1989), for the control of functional electrical stimulation (Graupe et al, 1988; Heftner et al, 1988), and in muscle fatigue studies (Kim and Lee, 1990; Kihwan and Minamitani, 1990; Zhou et al, 1990). AR modeling studies addressing the problem of muscle disease diagnosis are briefly reviewed.

Inbar and Noujaim - 1984

Inbar and Noujaim used an AR model of order twenty to characterize surface EMG (SEMG) recorded from the biceps at 50 percent of maximal voluntary contraction for clinical classification. The signal was sampled at 500Hz, and AR modeling was applied on stationary signal segments of 500ms length. The autocorrelation method was used to calculate the AR parameters. The normalized error test as well as the residual signal were used to find the optimal model order. It was found that twenty AR coefficients were adequate to give a reasonable segment approximation. Ten segments were taken to identify a record. The Fisher linear discriminant method was used for classification purposes on the 20x10 matrix of each subject. A classification score of 87,5 percent was achieved on a sample of three abnormal and five normal subjects as compared to the clinical needle classification. Results indicated that SEMG can be used successfully in diagnostic classification.

Lucas et al - 1986

Lucas, Doncarli, and Guiheneuc in 1986 developed a new computer-aided diagnostic approach in surface electromyography for diagnosis of neuromuscular diseases. They modeled the surface

EMG signal recorded during high level contractions by a second order ARMA process. The extended Kalman filter which is a recursive and adaptive identification method provided the parameters of the time varying ARMA model. A secondary filter gave also the variance of the residual noise. The trajectories of the four coefficients of the ARMA model and the variance of the residual noise were then used to classify the signal. Fisher discriminant analysis of the mean value of each trajectory of the above five parameters was carried out on about 30 normal and pathological cases during a ten seconds test. Results showed a classification performance of 82% of pathological and normal cases.

Paiss and Inbar - 1987

Paiss and Inbar investigated the ability of the AR model to describe SEMG recorded from the biceps brachii muscle. The stationarity of the SEMG signal was checked with the run test, at a level of significance of 5 percent. The signal was tested with intervals of variable length. Segment lengths of 0,64s were found to agree with the above requirement.

Power spectral curves were computed using the available data. First, the power spectrum of each block of 256 samples of the original signal was calculated by FFT. The resulting 100 periodograms were then averaged with 50 percent overlap to give the estimated SEMG spectrum. In turn, the AR model power spectrum was estimated for each block of 256 data points. In order to reduce the variance of the AR power spectrum, the 100 estimated AR power spectra were averaged. Both the FFT and the AR power spectra resembled each other with their general spectral envelope being attributed to the morphology of the MUAPs travelling along the muscle fibre, while the lower frequency peaks were determined by the motor units firing rate.

It was found that the AR model can fit the SEMG because of its peaky spectrum nature. The covariance method for the calculation of the AR coefficients, proved to be superior to the autocorrelation method both in accuracy and in speed. The AR and the reflection coefficients were plotted to track their time dependence. Oscillations in the graphs of the estimated coefficients as a function of time indicated that the calculated parameters suffered from a significant variance in their estimation process. The variance in the AR model order was expressed as large clusters of the poles location in the z-plane. The AR model order was selected using the AIC criterion and also by checking the whiteness of the residual signal. It was found that an order in the range of 2 to 6 was sufficient to describe the envelope of the SEMG, whereas a model order of 30 was required to identify the motor units firing rate.

With local muscular fatigue the SEMG shifted towards lower frequencies. The AR and reflection

coefficients of low orders together with the normalized residual energy declined with time. The trend of AR coefficient α_1 and reflection coefficient k_1 can be used for monitoring fatigue. During central fatigue caused by severe sleep deprivation, no consistent changes were observed in the SEMG spectrum or the AR parameters.

Mulavara et al - 1993

AR modeling was applied on SEMG recorded from the gastrocnemius muscle of healthy subjects during normal gait. The order of the model was selected using the AIC, and the Burg algorithm was used to calculate the AR coefficients. The order was found to be between 8 to 12. In the analysis the order chosen was 9. Frequencies at 60 and 130Hz were the dominant frequencies in the AR model power spectrum. The AR coefficients and the above frequencies seemed to be promising for the classification of normal and clinical subjects in the study of muscle contribution during gait. Further work would be carried out before using the results to distinguish normal and pathologic muscles.

2.4.2 Needle EMG

Coatrieux - 1983

In 1983 Coatrieux applied AR modeling on simulated and recorded EMG data. Both simulated and real data represented EMG activity of normal subjects. The experimental data was recorded from the extensor digitorum communis muscle at two different force levels using both surface and needle electrodes. The AR model order was determined using the Akaike (final prediction error), Kashyap, and Hannan test order functions (Jones, 1976; Roussel, 1980). The AR coefficients were estimated by the Yule-Walker equations either by inverting the autocorrelation matrix or recursively computed using the Levinson-Durbin algorithm and the Burg algorithm. The AR model validity was checked by residual noise analysis.

AR and FFT spectra were performed on the same data. Results indicated that the two spectra were in very good agreement except in the low frequency part. Differences in the spectra due to different force levels and recording modes were observed. These differences were expressed by an increase of high frequency power in the case of needle electrodes and in all frequency components at higher force levels. Coatrieux suggested that AR modeling can be used for diagnostic purposes by working on the AR coefficients or spectra shape.

Maranzana et al - 1984

Maranzana et al applied AR and ARMA modeling on simulated EMG signals of the biceps brachii muscle for diagnostic classification and data compression. Four significant pathological cases were

simulated: the myopathic, the normal, the recent neurogenic, and chronic neurogenic. AR model order selection has been carried out using the final prediction error (FPE), the Akaike information criterion (AIC), and the minimum description length (MDL) criteria. The Yule-Walker and the recursive least square (RLS) methods were used for determining the AR coefficients. Both methods gave equivalent results. Also residual analysis was carried out based on the Anderson and portmanteau tests (Box and Jenkins, 1976). In the ARMA analysis, model order was selected by means of the same criteria applied for the AR modeling. Also, diagnostic checking for the residual was the same as in the AR model case. The ARMA model had been implemented by using a batch algorithm described in Aström and Soderström (1979) and Bittanti (1981). The algorithm of Bauer and the Levenberg - Marquardt mechanism (Molinari and Sommariva, 1982) were also inserted in the programs to guarantee the stability in the estimation of the MA parameters.

Identification of the EMG signal corresponding to each class of pathology was initially tested by means of an AR model of order two. This was aiming at verifying whether only two AR parameters were capable of discriminating the pathologies. A low order model was selected due to the lower computational cost involved. The discrimination capability of the two identified parameters seemed encouraging.

In the data compression analysis one epoch of each simulated signal was attempted by AR models of order 1 to 9 and ARMA models of order (1, 1) to (3, 3). The goodness of the AR and ARMA models was verified by generating the signal from the identified parameters and the prediction error and comparing it with the original signal. The feasibility of data compression was tested by reconstructing the signal from the model parameters and generated white noise. From the signal, time and frequency domain parameters of clinical interest had been computed and compared with the values obtained from the original signal. Though identified parameters seemed unable to preserve the information in the time domain, their diagnostic yield was preserved. The frequency domain parameters of the original and reconstructed signals using FFT were compared and found to be in good agreement. The frequency parameters of the maximum Entropy (ME) spectra were also found in very good agreement with those obtained from the original and the reconstructed signals in all four pathological cases. Findings suggested replacement of the FFT algorithm, which requires averaging on a large number of power spectra for a reliable estimate, with the ME spectrum.

Basmajian et al - 1985

Basmajian and coworkers proposed AR modeling on MUAPs recorded from the tibialis anterior

muscle of a healthy subject using the monopolar needle. The power spectrum of each MUAP recorded was then obtained using the FFT and AR modeling of order 6. FFT and AR spectra were found to be in good correspondence. It was suggested that the method could be extended to the study of neuromuscular disorders.

In this study the AR model is preferred to MA and ARMA models for two reasons. First, it gives spectra which tend to have sharp peaks, a feature often associated with high resolution spectral estimates. Second, it results in simple linear equations for the estimation of the AR parameters. MA and ARMA parameters, on the other hand, can be calculated by a set of nonlinear equations which are lengthy and complex.

In this work, AR modeling is applied on MUAPs from the biceps brachii muscle at weak voluntary contraction using concentric needle electrodes. MUAPs are recorded from normal, myopathic, and neuropathic individuals. Stationarity of the EMG activity over the acquired length is checked by the run test and the reverse arrangements method. The optimum model order is determined by the AIC criterion, and the model parameters are identified by the modified covariance method. The model fitness is tested by residual noise study. This work is presented in Chapter 3. The correlation and diagnostic usefulness of various time domain parameters, AR spectral parameters, and AR and cepstral coefficients are assessed. Feature selection is performed using univariate and multivariate tests. Cluster analysis is also carried out using the K-means nearest neighbour and the Euclidean distance classifiers to determine the discrimination performance of various selected group of features from the above feature sets. Feature selection and cluster analysis findings are presented in Chapter 4.

2.5 Feature selection studies in needle EMG

Several features have been proposed in the literature to classify EMG signals for diagnostic purposes. Some of these features were ad hoc in nature. Although the diagnostic yield of each feature has often been reported, a quantitative measure for evaluating the effectiveness of these features has not been studied thoroughly yet. Recently, a number of EMG studies emerged with emphasis on features selection. A brief description of feature selection studies in needle EMG is cited below.

Stashuk and Naphan - 1990

Stashuk and Naphan, in a simulation study, examined the classification performance of different time and frequency domain MUAP features. The MUAPs analysed were extracted from three simulated myoelectric signals sampled at 25kHz. The MUAPs were extracted from five motor

units from each simulated myoelectric signal epoch created to approximate twenty percent maximum voluntary contractions. 256 samples were extracted for each MUAP. The mean value of each of the following MUAP feature representations were used as features for classification purposes:

- i) the middle 32, 25kHz high resolution MUAP time samples,
- ii) the middle 64, 25kHz high resolution time samples,
- iii) the middle 32, 12,5kHz Nyquist resolution time samples,
- iv) the complex frequency coefficients obtained by performing a 32 point FFT on the middle 32, 12,5kHz MUAP time samples, and
- v) the 32 power spectrum coefficients obtained by performing a 64 point FFT on the middle 32, 12,5kHz MUAP time samples.

For both the frequency and power spectrum features the mean value from the time domain signal representation was removed. The efficacy of each feature was assessed by calculating the apparent separation matrices (Heetderks, 1978) between features of the different motor units and by tracking the performance of a classification algorithm.

Averaged results for the three simulations showed that features obtained from the 32 frequency coefficients, the 32 Nyquist resolution time samples, and the 64 high resolution time samples all gave approximately equal performance. The feature obtained using the 32 high resolution time samples performed less favourably, while the 32 power samples feature gave the worst representation. This suggests that time and frequency analysis gave similar findings. High resolution time sample features provided no improvement of performance. In addition, the poor performance of the power coefficients feature suggests that phase information is generally important.

Pfeiffer and Kunze - 1993

Pfeiffer and Kunze studied the correlation and diagnostic usefulness of different time and frequency parameters of MUAPs recorded with concentric needle electrodes at low contraction levels. MUAPs were obtained from the biceps brachii, the rectus femoris, and the tibialis anterior muscles of normal, myopathic, and neuropathic individuals. Frequency domain parameters were computed from the FFT power spectrum which was performed on MUAPs of 512 data points. Frequency parameters included in the study were the centre frequency (*CF*), bandwidth (*BW*), and equivalent bandwidth (*BWE*). Additionally, the following five power measures, related to restricted frequency bands, were arbitrarily chosen aiming at diversity: relative power within the

frequency bands between 0 and 0,2kHz, between 1,2 and 1,4kHz, and between 1 and 1,6kHz, and absolute power within the bands between 0 and 0,6kHz and between 1 and 1,6kHz. Time domain parameters included in the study were the duration (Dur), spike duration (SpDur), area (Area), amplitude (Amp), phases (Ph), and 2 turn counts with amplitude limits of 25 and 50 μ V.

The correlation between parameters deduced from the frequency spectrum and conventional MUAP parameters was explored by principal component analysis. Most frequency parameters were redundant because of high correlation with conventional MUAP parameters and were subsequently discarded. The diagnostic usefulness of the remaining parameters was tested by stepwise variable selection algorithms for discriminant models classifying single MUAPs as neuropathic, myopathic or normal. The selection criterion was minimization of Wilks' lambda. Small values of Wilks' lambda are associated with good discriminant models and high rates of correctly classified MUAPs.

The *CF*, SpDur, Amp, Ph, Dur, and turn count with amplitude limit of 25 μ V were the parameters that formed the final parameter set. Discriminant models based on this set were given for the biceps brachii, the rectus femoris, and the tibialis anterior muscles of normal, neuropathic, and myopathic individuals. Results showed that *CF* was the most distinctive for the separation of myopathic and normal MUAPs. SpDur was particularly valuable for distinguishing between normal and neuropathic MUAPs. Results indicated that *CF* and SpDur are the most useful parameters and are recommendable for the classification of neuromuscular disorders.

Chapter 3

METHOD

This chapter describes the application of AR modeling on MUAPs recorded from normal individuals and subjects suffering from neuromuscular disorders. Features for discriminating various muscle pathologies are also discussed. Furthermore, the univariate and multivariate feature selection analysis methods are presented. Finally, the K-means nearest neighbour and the Euclidean distance classifiers are introduced. These classifiers evaluate the classification performance of selected features.

3.1 Introduction

AR modeling was applied on MUAPs recorded from normal individuals and subjects suffering from neuromuscular disorders. Individual MUAPs were identified and selected from the acquired EMG signal using a parametric pattern recognition algorithm (Pattichis, 1992). 512 data points were initially extracted from each MUAP at a sampling frequency of 20kHz. Further reduction of the sampling frequency by two gave MUAPs with 256 data points each. The mean value was subtracted from each MUAP before computing the FFT and AR power spectra. The stationarity of the signal over the acquired length was checked using the run and reverse arrangements tests before applying AR modeling. The model order computed was selected using the AIC, FPE, and MDL criteria. The AR coefficients were identified by the modified covariance method (Marple, 1987). The validity of the model was checked by examining the whiteness of the residuals.

Features extracted from the AR power spectra, AR and cepstral coefficients, and time parameters formed the four diagnostic feature sets. The univariate and the multivariate analysis methods together with the K-means nearest neighbour and the Euclidean distance classifiers were used to evaluate the classification performance of selected features. All the work described above is outlined in the flowchart of Figure 3.1.

1. EMG acquisition and time domain analysis
 - MUAP identification
 - MUAP selection
 - MUAP parametric pattern recognition
 - time domain features
 - duration (Dur), area (Area), spike duration (SpDur), spike area (SpArea), number of phases (Ph), number of turns (T), and amplitude (Amp)
2. MUAP set extraction
 - computation of averaged MUAP
 - epoch : 512 points, 25,6ms ($T = 50 \mu\text{s}$)
 - down sampling by two
 - mean value removed
3. FFT spectral estimation
 - Hamming window
 - zero padding
 - sample power spectrum
4. AR modeling
 - stationarity test
 - run and reverse arrangements tests
 - model order selection
 - FPE, AIC, and MDL criteria
 - normalized residual energy
 - modified covariance method
 - AR coefficients
 - AR model validity
 - normalized residuals periodogram
 - normalized cumulative residuals periodogram
 - portmanteau test statistic
5. AR spectral estimation
 - power measures
 - power levels at 100 (P_{100}), 200 (P_{200}), 300 (P_{300}), 500 (P_{500}), 750 (P_{750}), 1000 (P_{1000}), 1250 (P_{1250}), 1500 (P_{1500}), 2000 (P_{2000}), and 2500 (P_{2500}) Hz
 - frequency measures
 - peak power frequency (F_0), lower cut-off frequency (F_1), upper cut-off frequency (F_2), centre frequency (CF), median frequency ($FMED$), bandwidth (BW), quality factor (Q), and frequencies at -5 (F_5), -10 (F_{10}), -15 (F_{15}), -20 (F_{20}), and -25 (F_{25}) dB
 - spectral moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2
 - AR coefficients and model order p
 - cepstral coefficients
6. Statistical analysis
7. Feature selection analysis
 - Univariate and multivariate analysis methods
8. Cluster analysis
 - K-means nearest neighbour classifier
 - Euclidean distance classifier

Figure 3.1 Flowchart outlining the steps required to estimate the AR power spectral density, extract features from the AR spectra, and perform classification analysis for discriminating various muscle pathologies.

3.2 EMG acquisition and time domain analysis

In this study, the muscle studied was the biceps brachii, and the concentric needle electrode was used. EMG analysis in the time domain was implemented in four stages as given by Pattichis, 1992:

- i) Acquisition,
- ii) Identification,
- iii) Selection, and
- iv) Parametric pattern recognition (PPR) and classification.

3.2.1 Acquisition

The EMG signal was freely triggered, bandpass filtered at 3Hz to 10kHz, and sampled at 20kHz for 5 seconds with 12 bits resolution. The signal was then lowpass filtered at 8kHz.

3.2.2 Identification

Individual MUAPs were identified as follows:

- i) MUAP extraction,
- ii) MUAP baseline correction, and
- iii) MUAP measurement.

Figure 3.2 MUAP parameters.

For each identified potential the following seven parameters were measured (Figure 3.2):

- i) duration (MUAP beginning and ending are identified by sliding a measuring window of length 3ms and width $\pm 10\mu\text{V}$),
- ii) amplitude (difference between the minimum positive peak and the maximum negative peak),
- iii) area (sum of the rectified MUAP integrated over the duration measure),
- iv) phases (number of baseline crossings that exceed $25\mu\text{V}$ plus one),
- v) spike duration (measured from the first to the last positive peak),
- vi) spike area (sum of the rectified MUAP integrated over the spike duration), and
- vii) turns (number of positive and negative peaks separated from the preceding and following peak by $25\mu\text{V}$).

3.2.3 Selection

MUAPs were fed to the parametric pattern recognition algorithm if they satisfied the following criteria:

- i) Amplitude $\geq 50\mu\text{V}$,
- ii) Rise time $< 1,5\text{ms}$ (time interval between the minimum positive peak and the maximum negative peak),
- iii) Phases ≥ 2 , and
- iv) $1\text{ms} < \text{Duration} < 40\text{ms}$.

3.2.4 Parametric pattern recognition (PPR) and classification

The PPR algorithm tried to identify at least three MUAPs which belonged to the same group to form a set (Buchthal, 1957). The classification was based on the MUAP features: phases, amplitude, spike duration, and duration examined in sequence (Pattichis, 1992). For each subject a total of 20 MUAP sets were analysed using the PPR algorithm.

3.3 MUAP set extraction

MUAPs belonging to a set were averaged to obtain the averaged MUAP envelope. In the rest of the thesis, the averaged MUAP envelope is simply referred to as MUAP. A MUAP waveform consisted of 512 points (25,6ms), having the maximum peak in the region of 200 points (10ms).

3.3.1 Down sampling by two

The sampling rate of 20kHz was further reduced by 2 (as given in 3.2.1 the signal has already been lowpass filtered at 8kHz). This was implemented through software by rejecting every other point from the original 512 data points data sequence. As a result of this, the data sequence was

reduced to 256 points.

3.3.2 Mean value removed

The sample mean of each MUAP was computed and subtracted from each data point. If this is avoided spectral bias or distortion may result (Marple, 1987).

3.4 FFT spectral estimation

3.4.1 Hamming window

A data window is applied to the data in each MUAP prior to computation of the MUAP sample power spectrum. The purpose of the window is to reduce the effect of sidelobes and to decrease the estimation bias, at the price of a slight decrease in resolution. In this work the Hamming window is considered a reasonable selection following the results of Marple, 1987. The Hamming or raised cosine window is defined as

$$\omega(n) = 0,54 + 0,46 \cos(2\pi(-0,5 + n/N-1)) \quad \text{for} \quad 0 \leq n \leq N-1 \quad (3.1)$$

where N is the number of data samples (=256). MUAP data sequence $x(n)$ for $n=0$ to $n=N-1$ is first passed through the Hamming window. The windowed data sequence becomes

$$x_{\omega}(n) = x(n) \omega(n) \quad \text{for} \quad 0 \leq n \leq N-1. \quad (3.2)$$

3.4.2 Zero padding

In order to get a better estimation of the sample power spectrum, additional power points are calculated at a more dense set of frequencies. This is done by increasing the length of the windowed data sequence by means of zero padding. In this work zero values $x_{\omega}(N), \dots, x_{\omega}(4N-1)$ are added to the available N data samples. Therefore, the discrete Fourier transform (*DFT*) of the zero augmented $4N$ point windowed data sequence is

$$X(f) = T \sum_{n=0}^{4N-1} x_{\omega}(n) \exp(-j2\pi fnT) \quad (3.3)$$

where the range on the summation has been adjusted to reflect the zero samples, and T represents the sampling period (=100 μ s). It should be emphasized that zero padding does not improve the frequency resolution in the spectral estimate. Simply, it provides a method for interpolating power spectrum values at more frequencies. Zero padding gives a power spectral density (PSD) with a smoother appearance, removes ambiguities present in the non zero padded power spectrum, and estimates the frequency of the spectral peaks more accurately.

3.4.3 Sample power spectrum

The sample power spectrum of each MUAP is computed as

$$P_{xx}(f) = \frac{1}{UNT} |X(f)|^2 \quad (3.4)$$

$$\text{where } U = T \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \omega^2(n). \quad (3.5)$$

The factor U removes the effect of the window energy bias in the PSD estimator $P_{xx}(f)$.

The FFT power spectrum of each MUAP is also normalized by the maximum power value $P_{\max}$ computed among the estimated power points in each MUAP. The normalized PSD estimate of each MUAP, $P_{NORM}(f)$ then becomes

$$P_{NORM}(f) = \frac{P_{xx}(f)}{P_{\max}} \quad (3.6)$$

3.5 AR modeling

3.5.1 Stationarity test

AR modeling requires that the signal fitted be stationary over the given interval. This implies that its statistics would not vary over the given interval. The electromyogram, due to its random nature, is considered to be nonstationary. However, Makhoul has shown in 1975 that an AR model can be applied on a nonstationary process provided that the process can be classified as locally stationary or wide sense stationary. Bendat and Piersol in 1971 have described a practical test, the run test, which tests for wide sense stationarity. Various researchers demonstrated weak stationarity of the surface myoelectric signals over short time intervals using the above test (Kwatny et al, 1970; Inbar and Noujaim, 1984; Popivanov and Todorov, 1986; Hefftner, 1986). Also another useful procedure in the analysis of nonstationary data is the reverse arrangements method (Bendat and Piersol, 1986). This method checks if statistical independence or any underlying trend exists in the data to be analysed. It is more powerful than the run test for detecting monotonic rather than fluctuating trends in a sequence of observations.

Run test

The run test can be used to evaluate a sequence of observations for a trend. N_s observed values of a random variable X may be classified into one of two mutually exclusive categories which may be identified simply by plus (+) or minus (-). An example might be a sequence of measured values $x_i, i = 1, \dots, N_s$, with a mean value $\bar{x}$, where each observation is $x_i \geq \bar{x}$ (+) or $x_i < \bar{x}$ (-) or equivalently defined as $x_i - \bar{x} \geq 0$ (+) or $x_i - \bar{x} < 0$ (-).

A run, r , is defined as a sequence of identical observations that is followed and preceded by a different observation or no observation at all. Assuming the number of (+) observations equals the number of (-) observations, then the number of runs in the sequence will have a run distribution as given in Bendat and Piersol, 1986. The hypothesis can be tested at any desired level of significance α by comparing the observed runs to the interval between

$$r_{n;1-\alpha/2} < r \leq r_{n;\alpha/2} \quad \text{for} \quad n = \frac{N_s}{2}. \quad (3.7)$$

If the observed number of runs falls outside the interval, the hypothesis would be rejected at the α level of significance, otherwise, the hypothesis would be accepted.

In this work, the run test was used to check stationarity of the mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation (s) of all MUAPs in all disease subjects. The data for each MUAP were partitioned into 16 consecutive segments with 16 data points each. For each segment i , the average $\bar{x}_i$ and standard deviation s_i were estimated. The median value for all segments was then determined for each of the statistics. The deviation d from the median for each segment was calculated by

$$d_i^{\bar{x}} = \bar{x}_{median} - \bar{x}_i \quad \text{and} \quad (3.8)$$

$$d_i^s = s_{median} - s_i \quad \text{for } i=1, \dots, N_{seg}$$

where N_{seg} is the number of signal segments.

The number of sign changes of $d_i^{\bar{x}}$ ($d_i^{\bar{x}} \geq 0$ (+) and $d_i^{\bar{x}} < 0$ (-)) and d_i^s ($d_i^s \geq 0$ (+) and $d_i^s < 0$ (-)) were then compared with the range of sign changes that would occur in a truly stationary process. For a level of significance of $\alpha = 0.05$, r should lie between

$$r_{8,0,975} < r \leq r_{8,0,025} \quad \text{or} \quad 4 < r \leq 13. \quad (3.9)$$

Reverse arrangements test

As in the case of the run test, the reverse arrangements test was used to check the stationarity of the mean and standard deviation of all MUAPs in all subjects studied. MUAP data was partitioned into 16 segments with 16 data points each. For each segment i , $\bar{x}_i$ and s_i were estimated. In the reverse arrangements test the number of times that $\bar{x}_i > \bar{x}_j$ and $s_i > s_j$ for the mean and standard deviation statistics respectively is counted. i and j denote segments i and j respectively. Each such inequality is called a reverse arrangement. The total number of reverse

arrangements is denoted by A . The reverse arrangements test can be described mathematically as follows

$$h_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \bar{x}_i > \bar{x}_j \text{ or } s_i > s_j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, \dots, N_s. \quad (3.10)$$

$$\text{Then } A = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s-1} A_i \quad (3.11)$$

$$\text{where } A_i = \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_s} h_{ij} \quad (3.12)$$

and N_s is the number of data samples in each segment = 16.

The total number of reverse arrangements is then compared to the accepted region of reverse arrangements obtained from the reverse arrangements distribution (Bendat and Piersol, 1986) at a level of significance $\alpha=0,05$. The accepted region is

$$A_{N_s; 1-\alpha/2} < A \leq A_{N_s; \alpha/2}. \quad (3.13)$$

For $N_s=16$ and a significant level of $\alpha=0,05$ the equation above becomes

$$A_{16, 0,975} < A \leq A_{16, 0,025} \text{ or } 38 < A \leq 81. \quad (3.14)$$

3.5.2 Model order selection

Selection criteria

One important aspect in AR modeling is the selection of the model order p . A low model order gives a highly smoothed spectral estimate. On the other hand, a too high model order increases the resolution and introduces spurious low level peaks in the spectrum. Thus, the model order selection for AR spectral estimation is actually a trade-off of increased resolution and decreased variance.

One approach would be to construct AR models of increasing order until the computed prediction error variance reaches a minimum. However, all AR spectral estimators (Yule-Walker, Burg, covariance, and modified covariance methods) have prediction error (residual) variances that decrease monotonically with increasing order p . This, suggests that the linear prediction error variance is not sufficient alone to terminate the process unless a threshold value is imposed on the error variance. Another simple check concerning proper order selection is to visually inspect the residuals periodogram. The residuals periodogram should be white, and consequently an approximate flat periodogram estimate should be obtained.

Several criteria have been proposed in the literature for estimating the AR model order. Two criteria were proposed by Akaike, the final prediction error (FPE) and the Akaike information criterion (AIC) in 1969 and 1974 respectively. An alternative criterion, the minimum description length criterion (MDL), was proposed by Rissanen in 1983. A fourth criterion, the criterion autoregressive transfer (CAT) function, was proposed by Parzen in 1974. Experimental results indicated that none of the above cited criteria gave definitive results, particularly when applied to actual data rather than simulated AR processes (Gersch and Sharpe, 1973; Ulrych and Bishop, 1975; Tong, 1975, 1977; Jones, 1976; Nuttall, 1976; Berryman, 1978; Kaveh and Bruzzone, 1979; Kashyap, 1980). This suggests that various model orders using different criteria should be tried, and finally their findings should be compared against each other.

In this study the FPE, AIC, and MDL criteria were used for estimating the optimum model order. In all criteria the model order is determined by choosing that order which minimizes the selection criterion function.

The FPE criterion is defined as

$$\text{FPE}(p) = \hat{\sigma}_p^2 \left(\frac{N+p+1}{N-p-1} \right) \quad (3.15)$$

where p is the AR model order, N is the number of data samples, and $\hat{\sigma}_p^2$ is the estimated linear prediction error variance for the model with order p . In this work the linear prediction error variance was considered to be an estimate of the white noise variance $\hat{\sigma}_w^2$ in an AR process.

The AIC criterion selects the model order by minimizing

$$\text{AIC}(p) = N \ln(\hat{\sigma}_p^2) + 2p. \quad (3.16)$$

Since the AIC has a tendency to overestimate the correct order as the data record length increases (Kashyap, 1980), the MDL criterion has been developed by Rissanen and has the form

$$\text{MDL}(p) = N \ln(\hat{\sigma}_p^2) + p \ln(N). \quad (3.17)$$

The second term in the formulae that describe the AIC and the MDL criteria represents the penalty for using higher orders without significantly reducing the prediction error variance.

Normalized residual energy

In order to compare the results of the different model orders chosen by FPE, AIC, and MDL criteria the normalized residual energy was estimated by

$$e_{NORM} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (\hat{e}(n) - \bar{e})^2}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (x(n) - \bar{x})^2}. \quad (3.18)$$

The residual error estimate $\hat{e}(n)$ was computed as the difference between the actual signal $x(n)$ and the predicted signal $\hat{x}(n)$ and is expressed mathematically as

$$\hat{e}(n) = x(n) - \hat{x}(n)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{x}(n) = - \sum_{k=1}^p a_k x(n-k). \quad (3.19)$$

Also, $\bar{e}$ and $\bar{x}$ represent the mean values of the residual error estimate and the actual signal respectively.

3.5.3 Modified covariance method

AR coefficients

There are a number of methods for determining the coefficients of an AR process when a block of data samples is available such as the Yule-Walker, the Burg, the covariance, and the modified covariance methods. Certain problems associated with spectra determined from AR parameter estimators, such as spurious spectral peaks, frequency estimation biases, and spectral line splitting, are factors that need to be considered in choosing one of the above methods.

AR spectral estimates tend to exhibit spurious peaks when the model order is overestimated. Model order selection criteria can be used to eliminate spurious peaks. Lowering model order in an attempt to prevent spurious peaks results in the reduction of resolution. Among the methods given above, the Burg, the covariance, and the modified covariance methods tend to have better resolution for a given order than the Yule-Walker method which suffers the most degradation in resolution of all methods due to the windowing effects present in this technique (Marple, 1987).

Also, the Burg and the Yule-Walker methods suffer from line splitting. This means that two or more closely spaced peaks can occur in the spectral estimate in certain cases. The modified covariance spectrum, based on the same data sequence as in the other two methods, yields a single peak at the correct frequency (Fougere et al, 1976).

Several problems with the Burg method, including spectral line splitting and bias of the frequency estimate, appear to be eliminated when the modified covariance method is used. Also the

modified covariance algorithm is computational comparable with the Burg algorithm. For $p \ll N$, the modified covariance algorithm is actually more efficient than the Burg algorithm when the same order is used for both algorithms (Marple, 1987). All the above advantages justified the use of the modified covariance method in this study for the estimation of the AR parameters. The modified covariance method gains its importance over the Burg method from the fact that it performs a minimization of the average forward and backward linear prediction squared errors with respect to all the prediction coefficients. On the other hand, the Burg method performs a constrained least squares minimization with respect to a single prediction coefficient α_p (p) which is nothing else than the reflection coefficient k_p (Marple, 1987). The estimation of the AR parameters using the modified covariance method is analysed in Appendix 1. In this work the modified covariance algorithm and code program as given by Marple (1987) was used for the computation of the AR parameter estimates.

3.5.4 AR model validity

Normalized residuals periodogram

After a model order has been selected and the AR coefficients have been estimated, the next important step is to check how well the AR model fits the data. The model fitness can be tested by computing the residuals $\hat{e}(n)$ between the actual signal $x(n)$ and the predicted signal $\hat{x}(n)$ for $n = 0, \dots, N-1$. If the residuals are really a white noise process, then the AR model fits the data satisfactorily.

First, the periodogram of the residuals $\hat{e}(n)$ for $n = 0, \dots, N-1$ can be computed using

$$P_e(f_i) = \frac{1}{NT} \left| T \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \hat{e}(n) \exp(-j2\pi f_i nT) \right|^2 \quad \text{for } i=0, \dots, N-1. \quad (3.20)$$

The shape of the periodogram is visually examined if it broadly behaves like the periodogram of a white noise process.

Normalized cumulative residuals periodogram

Another test that can be carried out for checking the whiteness of the residuals is by using the normalized cumulative residuals periodogram $C(f_i)$ which is defined as

$$C(f_i) = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^i P_e(f_i)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} P_e(f_i)} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^i P_e(f_i)}{NS^2} \quad \text{for } i = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (3.21)$$

where s^2 is an estimate of the residuals $\hat{\epsilon}(n)$ variance. The s^2 is estimated using the large sample estimate,

$$s^2 = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (x(n) - \hat{x}(n))^2 / (N-1). \quad (3.22)$$

The $C(f_i)$ can then be plotted versus the f_i , with f_i being normalized to the sampling frequency that is 10kHz. For a perfect fit all of the data would lie along a line connecting the points (0, 0) and (0,5, 1). Acceptable deviations from this line for an underlying white noise process are given in Box and Jenkins, 1976.

Portmanteau test statistic

The order of the fitted model can also be checked by using the portmanteau test statistic (Box and Jenkins, 1976). This test calculates a value Q according to the formula

$$Q = N \sum_{n=1}^m \hat{\epsilon}^2(n) \quad (3.23)$$

where N is the number of residuals, and

m is the number of lags in the estimation of the residuals autocorrelation function.

Common values for m are 12 or 24 (Hefftner et al, 1988). In this work m was chosen to be 24.

Q is approximately distributed as a chi-square distribution having $(m-p)$ degrees of freedom.

Thus, a test of the hypothesis of model adequacy can be made by referring the value of Q to a table of chi-square values. The hypothesis is accepted at a significance level of $\alpha=0,05$ if the value of Q is less than the value in the table for $(m-p)$ degrees of freedom i.e.,

$$Q < \chi_{\alpha, (m-p)}^2. \quad (3.24)$$

3.6 AR spectral estimation

3.6.1 AR spectrum

In the AR model the random process $x(n)$ is given as the output of a linear filter that models the observed data excited by an input driving sequence. The driving sequence is not usually available for purposes of spectral analysis. It could be assumed to be a unit impulse, an impulse train, or white noise. In this study, it is assumed that the driving sequence is a white noise process of zero mean and variance ρ_w . The random process $x(n)$ is realized by

$$x(n) = - \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k x(n-k) + w(n) \quad (3.25)$$

where $x(n)$ is the random process, α_k 's are the AR coefficients, p is the AR model order, and $w(n)$ is the white noise sequence.

The above equation when transformed in the frequency domain becomes

$$X(f) = - \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k X(f) e^{-j2\pi f k T} + W(f)$$

or
$$X(f) + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k X(f) e^{-j2\pi f k T} = W(f)$$

or
$$X(f) \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k e^{-j2\pi f k T} \right) = W(f)$$

or
$$X(f) = \frac{W(f)}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k e^{-j2\pi f k T}}$$

Taking the square of both sides in the above equation, the autoregressive PSD estimate becomes

$$P_{AR}(f) = |X(f)|^2$$

$$\text{or } P_{AR}(f) = \frac{P_{ww}(f)}{\left| 1 + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k e^{-j2\pi f k T} \right|^2} \quad (3.26)$$

where $P_{ww}(f) = |W(f)|^2$ is the PSD of the white noise sequence and is given as

$$P_{ww}(f) = T \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} r_{ww}(n) e^{-j2\pi f n T}$$

$$\text{or } P_{ww}(f) = T \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} w(n) w(n) e^{-j2\pi f n T}.$$

The white noise sequence of zero mean is uncorrelated with itself for all lags, except at $n=0$, for which its variance is ρ_w . The equation above becomes

$$P_{ww}(f) = T \rho_w. \quad (3.27)$$

Substituting (3.27) in (3.26), $P_{AR}(f)$ takes the form

$$P_{AR}(f) = \frac{T \rho_w}{\left| 1 + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k e^{-j2\pi f k T} \right|^2}. \quad (3.28)$$

The estimation of the AR model parameters depends on the availability of the autocorrelation sequence of the random process. However, the autocorrelation is not known, so an AR spectral estimate must be made from the available data. In this work, the modified covariance method is used which produces AR model parameter estimates and in turn evaluates the AR PSD function. The modified covariance method actually makes estimates of the linear prediction coefficients by performing a combined minimization of the forward and backward linear prediction squared errors. The linear prediction coefficients are then used as the AR parameters estimates. Once the AR parameters are estimated, the AR power spectral density estimate is computed as

$$\hat{P}_{AR}(f) = \frac{T \hat{\rho}_w}{\left| 1 + \sum_{k=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_k e^{-j2\pi f k T} \right|^2} \quad (3.29)$$

in which $\hat{\rho}_w$ is an estimate of the driving noise variance which is provided by the modified covariane method. In this study the program as given by Marple (1987) was used for the computation of the AR power spectral density estimate.

Before calculating the AR power spectral density estimate the mean value is subtracted from each MUAP. Also $p+1$ to $4N$ zero values are added to the autoregressive coefficients sequence so as to extrapolate more power spectrum values at a more dense set of frequencies. The benefits of zero padding are given in section 3.4.2. It is noted that frequency resolution in the spectral estimate is not enhanced by zero padding. Finally, the AR power spectrum of each MUAP is normalized by the maximum power value present in each MUAP.

- | | |
|-------|--|
| i) | Power levels at 100 (P_{100}), 200 (P_{200}), 300 (P_{300}), 500 (P_{500}), 750 (P_{750}), 1000 (P_{1000}), 1250 (P_{1250}), 1500 (P_{1500}), 2000 (P_{2000}), and 2500 (P_{2500}) Hz. |
| ii) | Peak power frequency (F_0). |
| iii) | Frequencies at lower (F_1) and upper (F_2) -3dB points. |
| iv) | Bandwidth (BW). |
| v) | Quality factor (Q). |
| vi) | Frequencies at -5 (F_5), -10 (F_{10}), -15 (F_{15}), -20 (F_{20}), and -25 (F_{25}) dB following F_0 . |
| vii) | Centre frequency (CF). |
| viii) | Median frequency ($FMED$). |
| ix) | Moments of order 0 (M_0), 1 (M_1), and 2 (M_2). |

Figure 3.3 Features extracted from the AR spectrum.

3.6.2 AR spectral measures

Various frequency and power measures were derived from the AR power spectrum of each MUAP. These measures after being assessed will be used for the diagnosis of muscle pathology. Features that were extracted from the AR spectra are also shown in Figure 3.3.

Several of the above listed features are self explanatory and need no further explanation. Features that require further discussion are given underneath.

Bandwidth (BW) is the difference of frequencies at the upper and lower -3dB points of the power spectrum and is given as

$$BW = F_2 - F_1 \quad (3.30)$$

where F_2 and F_1 are the upper and lower cut-off frequencies respectively.

Quality factor (Q) is the ratio of the dominant peak frequency F_0 divided by the BW and is expressed as

$$Q = \frac{F_0}{BW} \quad (3.31)$$

where F_0 is the frequency at 0dB power level.

Moments of order 0, 1, and 2: A moment M_j of order j is defined by Lindstrom and Petersen (1983) as

$$M_j = \frac{2}{(2\pi)^{j+1}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(n)^j P_{AR}(f(n)) \quad (3.32)$$

Therefore, moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 can be computed for $j = 0, 1$, and 2 by

$$M_0 = \frac{2}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} P_{AR}(f(n)) \quad (3.33)$$

$$M_1 = \frac{2}{(2\pi)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(n) P_{AR}(f(n)) \quad \text{and} \quad (3.34)$$

$$M_2 = \frac{2}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (f(n))^2 P_{AR}(f(n)). \quad (3.35)$$

Centre frequency (CF) or mean power frequency can be obtained from the following formulae:

$$CF = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(n)P_{AR}(f(n))}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} P_{AR}(f(n))} \quad (3.36)$$

or it can be equivalently given as the ratio of moments M_1 and M_0

$$CF = \frac{M_1}{M_0}. \quad (3.37)$$

Median Frequency (FMED) is the frequency at which the power spectrum is divided into two regions with equal power, and can be computed using the formula

$$\sum_{n=0}^{FMED-1} P_{AR}(f(n)) = \sum_{n=FMED}^{N-1} P_{AR}(f(n)). \quad (3.38)$$

3.6.3 AR coefficients

As it was mentioned earlier orders from 2 to 20 were evaluated using the different selection criteria. Once the optimum model order was selected, the AR coefficients for each MUAP were computed using the modified covariance method. The AR coefficients were then used to estimate the AR power spectral density estimate. The AR coefficients were also used as diagnostic features for classification purposes.

3.6.4 Cepstral coefficients

There are two forms of cepstra, the complex cepstrum and the real cepstrum. The complex cepstrum c_{n_c} is defined as the inverse Fourier transform of the logarithm of the Fourier transform of the data sequence $x(n)$ and is expressed as

$$c_{n_c} = IDFT \{ \ln [DFT (x(n))] \}. \quad (3.39)$$

The real cepstrum c_{n_r} is defined as the inverse Fourier transform of the logarithm of the magnitude of the data sequence $x(n)$, and it has the form

$$c_{n_r} = IDFT \{ \ln | DFT (x(n)) | \}. \quad (3.40)$$

Suffices c and r in equations (3.39) and (3.40) respectively are used to distinguish complex from real cepstrum. Although in defining the cepstra any base can be used for the logarithm, the natural logarithm (i.e., base e) is typically used.

The real cepstral coefficients can also be derived directly from the AR coefficients using the formulae underneath (Bishnu, 1976). For simplicity the suffix is dropped from the real cepstrum coefficients.

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_1 &= -\alpha_1 \\
 c_n &= -\alpha_n - \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1-k/n) \alpha_k c_{n-k} \quad \text{for } 1 < n \leq p \quad \text{and} \\
 c_n &= - \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1 - k/n) \alpha_k c_{n-k} \quad \text{for } n > p
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.41}$$

where α_n and c_n denote the n th AR and cepstral coefficients respectively.

This approach is found much more convenient and efficient, and it is used in this study for the estimation of the cepstral coefficients. Cepstral coefficients were estimated for each MUAP from the AR coefficients so as to use them for disease diagnosis. Cepstral coefficients have also been found to be more effective than AR coefficients in speech recognition (Atal, 1976).

3.7 Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics for selected time and AR spectral parameters were computed using the univariate and the multivariate statistical analysis methods.

3.7.1 Univariate statistical analysis

One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out for the following parameters: duration, spike duration, amplitude, turns, peak power frequency, centre frequency, median frequency, bandwidth, quality factor, and moments of order 0, 1, and 2. The hypothesis that parameter means are equal for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups was carried out at a significant level of $\alpha=0,05$. Pair difference t-test analysis was also carried out between the NOR-MND, NOR-MYO, and MYO-MND groups at a significant level of $\alpha=0,05$.

3.7.2 Multivariate statistical analysis

Correlation analysis was carried out to investigate the interrelationship between various parameters. Selected time domain parameters that are not highly correlated (Pattichis, 1992) were combined with selected features extracted from the AR spectra, and correlation analysis was carried out to investigate their interdependency. The correlation between parameters of the following feature sets was performed so as to form the final set of features for feature selection analysis:

- i) duration, spike duration, amplitude, and number of turns,

- ii) peak power frequency, centre frequency, median frequency, bandwidth, quality factor, moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 , and
- iii) model order p .

3.8 Feature selection analysis

Several features have been proposed in the literature by various researchers for the EMG signature discrimination. Although the classification ability of each feature or of the different feature sets has often been reported, quantitative analysis for evaluating their effectiveness has not been studied thoroughly yet. In this study two feature selection strategies are considered, namely: i) the univariate (Univar) and ii) the multivariate covariance (M-covar) methods (Rauber et al, 1993).

3.8.1 Univariate analysis

The Univar method ignores the interdependency among the features and analyses them one at a time. A separability criterion is calculated for each feature, and the features are then ordered according to this criterion.

Criterion function

The normalized probabilistic distance d_i between the feature value x_i for class i and the class mean $\bar{x}_i$ is defined as

$$d_i = \frac{|x_i - \bar{x}_i|}{s_i} \quad (3.42)$$

where s_i is the standard deviation of class i .

The normalized probabilistic distance d between the means $\bar{x}_i$ and $\bar{x}_j$ of the two adjacent classes i and j is given as

$$d = \frac{\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j}{s_i + s_j} \quad \text{for} \quad \bar{x}_i > \bar{x}_j \quad (3.43)$$

where s_i and s_j are the standard deviations for classes i and j respectively.

As s_i and s_j decrease, and the distance between $\bar{x}_i$ and $\bar{x}_j$ increases, distance d becomes higher. Big values of d actually express a great interclass distance between the two classes i and j . It may be shown, using Chebychev's inequality (Bendat and Piersol, 1986), that

$$P [d_i \geq d] \leq \frac{1}{d^2}. \quad (3.44)$$

This probability should be as small as possible. A small probability indicates that the feature value lies nearer to its own class than to the other class. Hence, the term $\frac{1}{d^2}$ should be minimal

for a highly discriminative feature. Equation (3.44) is equivalent to

$$P [d_i < d] \leq 1 - \frac{1}{d^2} \quad (3.45)$$

$$\text{or} \quad P [d_i < d] \leq 1 - \left(\frac{s_i + s_j}{\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j} \right)^2. \quad (3.46)$$

Thus, the above equation can be used to establish a class separability measure Δ between the two classes (Kononenko and Roskar, 1984)

$$\Delta (i,j) = 1 - \left(\frac{s_i + s_j}{\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j} \right)^2. \quad (3.47)$$

This distance measure indicates how well a certain feature can distinguish between the two classes. The optimum value of the above separability measure is one and implies that the two classes are well separated. Negative values indicate class overlapping. The Univar criterion is finally obtained by averaging all mutual distances between all classes and is expressed as

$$\text{Criterion (Univar)} = \frac{2}{k(k-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^k \Delta (i,j) \quad (3.48)$$

where k is the number of classes=3.

Once the criterion is calculated, features are ranked according to this criterion. Finally, the best features are selected. This feature selection criterion is limited that it cannot detect highly correlated features. This suggests that correlation analysis should be carried out first before applying the univariate analysis method.

3.8.2 Multiple covariance analysis

The multiple covariance (M-Covar) analysis takes into account the dependence among the features. The M-Covar algorithm chooses one arbitrary feature from the whole group of features, as the first

control variable, and for each of the unselected features calculates the univariate F-Ratio. It then orders all features following the M-Covar criterion. The feature with the highest criterion value is passed to the controls and substitutes the first which was initially selected arbitrarily. The above process is repeated for all unselected features. At each iteration the selected feature with the highest F-Ratio joins the already selected features until the desired number of selected features is reached. Details of the multiple covariance analysis method can be found in Michalski and Larson, 1978.

Criterion function

In the multivariate covariance analysis the "total" matrix T is calculated as the sum of "among-classes" matrix A and the "within-classes" matrix W satisfying the equation

$$T = A + W.$$

$$T = \sum_{k=1}^{\hat{\theta}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} \mathbf{x}_{k_i} \mathbf{x}_{k_i}^T \quad (3.49)$$

$$A = \sum_{k=1}^{\hat{\theta}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} (\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) (\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k - \bar{\mathbf{x}})^T \quad (3.50)$$

$$W = \sum_{k=1}^{\hat{\theta}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} (\mathbf{x}_{k_i} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) (\mathbf{x}_{k_i} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k - \bar{\mathbf{x}})^T \quad (3.51)$$

where $\hat{\theta}$ = number of classes from $k=1, \dots, \hat{\theta}$

N_k = number of subjects of class k

N_i = number of subjects in all classes

m = number of control variables (number of already selected features)

ℓ = number of predictor variables (ℓ is always 1)

$\mathbf{x}_{k_i} = (x_{1,k_i}, \dots, x_{m,k_i}, x_{\ell,k_i})$ is a feature vector of subject i in class k and consists of the m already selected features and the control feature ℓ (3.52)

$\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k$ = local centroid for class k

$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ = global centroid for all classes

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} \mathbf{x}_{k_i} \quad (3.53)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{k=1}^{\vartheta} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} \mathbf{x}_{k_i}. \quad (3.54)$$

Matrices T and W can be split following the schema underneath

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } W = \begin{bmatrix} W_{11} & W_{12} \\ W_{21} & W_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.55)$$

where $(m-1, m-1)$, $(m-1, 1)$, $(1, m-1)$, and $(1, 1)$ are the dimensions of the sub-matrices T_{11} , T_{12} , T_{21} and T_{22} respectively. The dimensions of W sub-matrices are analogous.

Then, the total residual matrix $T_{2,1}$ and the within residual matrix $W_{2,1}$ are defined as

$$T_{2,1} = T_{22} - T_{21} T_{11}^{-1} T_{12} \quad (3.56)$$

$$W_{2,1} = W_{22} - W_{21} W_{11}^{-1} W_{12}. \quad (3.57)$$

Finally, the j th univariate F-Ratio is defined as

$$F_j = \frac{(t_{2,1j} - w_{2,1j}) / f_1}{(w_{2,1j} / f_2)} \quad (3.58)$$

with $f_1 = \vartheta - 1$ degrees of freedom for the numerator and $f_2 = N_t - \vartheta - m$ being the degrees of freedom for the denominator. Since the number of predictors ℓ is always 1 the index j can only have the value of 1. Therefore, the feature selection criterion for the multiple covariance analysis method is defined as

$$\text{Criterion (M-covar)} = F_1. \quad (3.59)$$

The computational time required for the M-covar algorithm is higher than that of the Univar algorithm. The advantage of the method is that it represents highly correlated features by only one discriminative feature. The rest of the features are classified as features with low univariate F-ratio.

3.9 Cluster analysis

Clustering is the grouping of similar objects. Given a number of measures cluster analysis aims in devising a classification scheme for grouping these measures into a number of classes such that

measures within classes are similar and unlike those from other classes (Everitt, 1981). The number of classes and the characteristics of each class are to be determined by the algorithm. It should be emphasized that cluster analysis deals with the classification from initially unclassified data (also known as unsupervised pattern recognition) in contrast to discriminant function analysis (sort of supervised pattern recognition) which handles the assigning of individuals to previously established classes.

3.9.1 *K-means nearest neighbour classifier*

In this study the K-means nearest neighbour clustering algorithm (Tou and Gonzalez, 1981) was used to classify the following group of features obtained from the normal, MND, and myopathy subjects: i) Dur, SpDur, Ph, Amp, ii) α_1 to α_5 , iii) α_1 to α_{12} iv) c_1 to c_3 , v) c_1 to c_{12} , vi) p , and vii) CF , $FMED$, F_0 , BW , Q , M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 . Twenty four of the 40 subjects in this study have been arbitrarily selected to form the training set (8 subjects from each group), and the rest 16 subjects have been used for the evaluation set. The selection was random and no predefined criteria were used for assigning a subject to the training or the evaluation set. The classification performance of the above group of features was investigated first for the training set, and then the trained models were evaluated using the evaluation set. In this work, the statistical package SYSTAT was used to perform the K-means clustering analysis. The number of clusters K was chosen to be three, equal to the number of diseases investigated. The performance of the K-means nearest neighbour classifier for both the training and evaluation sets was evaluated by computing the percentage of correct classifications (% CCs), false positives (% FPs), and false negatives (% FNs) by using

$$\%CCs = 100 (TP + TN)/N_t \quad (3.60)$$

$$\%FPs = 100 (FP/(TN + FP)) \quad (3.61)$$

$$\%FNs = 100 (FN/(TP + FN)) \quad (3.62)$$

where TP is the number of true positives, FP the number of false positives, TN the number of true negatives, FN the number of false negatives, and N_t the total number of subjects. A true positive was an abnormal subject classified as abnormal, while a false positive was a normal subject classified as abnormal. Similarly, a true negative is a normal subject classified as normal, while a false negative is an abnormal subject classified as normal. Also, sensitivity (SE), specificity (SP), positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were estimated using the following equations (Feinstein, 1977)

$$SE = 100 (TP/(TP + FN)) \quad (3.63)$$

$$SP = 100 (TN / (TN + FP)) \quad (3.64)$$

$$PPV = 100 (TP / (TP + FP)) \quad (3.65)$$

$$NPV = 100 (TN / (TN + FN)). \quad (3.66)$$

3.9.2 Euclidean distance classifier

Similarly, the Euclidean distance (ED) classifier was used to evaluate the classification performance of the group of features listed in section 3.9.1 for both the training and evaluation sets. For each subject an ED measure is calculated for each group of features by adding the square of the difference between each parameter in the group and the mean of its class. This ED measure is described mathematically as follows

$$ED_{k_j} = \sum_{i=1}^l (x_{k_j}(i) - \bar{x})^2 \quad (3.67)$$

where ED_{k_j} = ED of subject j belonging to class k

$x_{k_j}(i)$ = feature value $x(i)$ of subject j in class k

k = class number, 1 = NOR, 2 = MND, 3 = MYO

j = 1, ..., N_k

l = number of features in each group

N_k = number of subjects in each class

$\bar{x}_k$ = mean of class k and is defined as

$$\bar{x}_k = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{j=1}^{N_k} x_{k_j}. \quad (3.68)$$

This ED measure is then compared to the ED measures obtained in a similar manner as described above but now subtracting from each parameter in the group the mean of each of the remaining classes to which the subject is not belonging. These ED measures are given as

$$ED_{n_j} = \sum_{i=1}^l (x_{k_j}(i) - \bar{x}_n)^2 \text{ for } n \neq k \quad (3.69)$$

where $\bar{x}_n$ is the mean of class to which the subject does not belong and is defined as

$$\bar{x}_n = \frac{1}{N_n} \sum_{j=1}^{N_n} x_{n_j} \text{ for } n \neq k. \quad (3.70)$$

The subject under study is then classified as belonging to its own class if $ED_k < ED_n$, for all classes for which $k \neq n$. The analysis is repeated for all subjects, and the number of correct classifications are then counted and reported.

The performance of the Euclidean distance classifier was assessed by computing the percentage of correct classifications, false positives, and false negatives. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value were also estimated.

Chapter 4

RESULTS

A total of 800 MUAPs were recorded from the brachial biceps muscle from 40 subjects using the concentric needle electrode. Three groups of subjects were examined: normal, MND, and myopathic. Spectral analysis was carried out using AR modeling and the FFT. Spectral measures were extracted from the AR model power spectra and combined with time domain parameters for EMG diagnosis. These features were then subjected to univariate and multivariate statistical analysis. Correlation analysis between AR spectral and time domain parameters was carried out. Highly correlated features were dropped out, and feature selection analysis was carried out on the remaining parameters using the univariate and the multivariate covariance analysis methods. The K-means nearest neighbour and the Euclidean distance classifiers were also used to evaluate the classification performance of selected group of features.

4.1 Material

Neuromuscular diseases is a group of disorders that involve the motor nuclei of the cranial nerves, the anterior horn cells of the spinal cord, the nerve roots and spinal nerves, the peripheral nerves, the neuromuscular junction, and the muscle itself (Walton, 1992). These disorders cause muscular weakness and/or wasting. From the large number of neuromuscular disorders that have been identified, two groups have been selected for this study as their consistency of clinical appearance is good. These are motor neuron disease and myopathy.

•**Motor Neuron Disease (MND)**, is a disease causing selective degeneration of the upper and lower motor neuron. This disease affects middle to old aged people, with progressive widespread loss of motor neurons usually leading to death within three to five years. In the advanced stages of this disease large motor units also denervate. Motor unit potentials with duration values that are longer than normal and with increased amplitude are typical findings in MND. Their occurrence reflects an increase in the number or density of fibers in motor units, or increased temporal dispersion of the activity picked up by the recording electrode. The latter effect is the result of slowed conduction along the terminal branches of individual nerve fibers, or increase in the end-plate zone, or both.

•**Myopathies (MYO)**, are a group of diseases that affect primarily skeletal muscle fibers and are divided into two groups, according to whether they are inherited or acquired. Most muscular

dystrophies are hereditary causing severe degenerative changes in the muscle fibers. In this group of diseases, there are four main types of muscular dystrophy namely Duchenne's, Becker's, fascioscapulohumeral, and limb girdle. They show a progressive clinical course from birth or after a variable period of apparently normal infancy. One most frequent acquired myopathy is polymyositis that is characterized by acute or subacute onset, with muscle weakness progressing slowly over a matter of weeks. MUAPs with short duration and reduced amplitude are typical findings in patients suffering from myopathy. These findings are attributed to fiber loss within the motor unit, with the degree of reduction of these parameters reflecting the amount of fiber loss (Trojaborg, 1992).

In this study, a total of 800 MUAPs were collected from the biceps brachii muscle from 12 normal, 15 MND, and 13 MYO subjects using the concentric needle electrode. The EMG data used in this study has been taken from the data available at the Department of Clinical Neurophysiology of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics. The three disease groups are summarised in Table 4.1. Diagnostic criteria for the subjects selected were based on clinical opinion, biochemical data, and muscle biopsy. Only subjects with no history or signs of neuromuscular disorders were included in the normal group. Furthermore, the biceps brachii muscle was examined because it is a proximal muscle of the shoulder girdle that is usually affected at an early stage in both MND and MYO. Also, its easy accessibility has made it attractive to study and widely reported in the literature.

MUAP findings in the time domain for the three groups under consideration are briefly discussed (Pattichis, 1992). The mean, median, standard deviation, lower quartile (Q_1), upper quartile (Q_3), and semi-interquartile range (SIQR) for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups are given in Tables 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4 respectively. Mean and standard deviation of duration of normal subjects is $10,15 \pm 2,80$ ms and mean and standard deviation of amplitude is $0,40 \pm 0,32$ mV. Myopathy patients usually have MUAPs with short duration, low amplitude, and small number of phases, whereas MND patients have MUAPs with long duration, high amplitude, and a large number of phases.

Twenty four of the 40 cases in this study have been randomly selected to form the training set (8 subjects from each group), and the remaining 16 subjects were used for evaluating the performance of the models after training. The selection was random i.e., no criteria were used for assigning a subject either to the training set or to the evaluation set. These sets were used for cluster analysis.

Typical EMG data for a NOR, MND, and MYO subjects are given in Figures 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3 respectively.

4.2 AR modeling

4.2.1 Stationarity

The stationarity of the EMG data, a requirement for successful application of AR modeling, has been investigated by the run test and the reverse arrangements method. The results of the stationarity test for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups are given in Tables 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7 respectively. Results showed that MUAPs analysed by their mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation(s) values can be generally considered in the wide sense stationary. In the case of the $\bar{x}$ statistic, both the run test and the reverse arrangements test performed equally well for all subjects. For the NOR group the mean of the percentage of potentials that passed the stationarity test for the $\bar{x}$ statistic was 92% for the run test, and 96% for the reverse arrangements test. Similar results were obtained for the MND group as given in Table 4.6, whereas for the MYO group the percentage of potentials that passed the stationarity test dropped shightly, as shown in Table 4.7. For the s statistic, for the NOR group, the percentage of potentials that passed the stationarity test was 75% and 87% for the run test and reverse arrangement test respectively. These values were slightly lower for the MND group, and slightly higher for the MYO group, as given in Tables 4.6 and 4.7 respectively.

4.2.2 Model order selection

The mean and standard deviation values of the optimal model orders as well as the normalized residual energies for the AIC, FPE, and MDL criteria of each subject studied are listed in Tables 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10 for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups respectively. For the NOR group the AIC criterion yielded model orders in the range of 5,250 to 8,000 whereas the MDL criterion gave orders ranging from 3,550 to 4,600. A similar picture prevailed also in case of the MND and MYO groups with higher orders obtained in the case of the AIC criterion compared to the MDL criterion. When the mean optimal model orders are considered, there is 32% decrease in model orders using the MDL criterion in the NOR group compared to model orders obtained by the AIC criterion. Similar results were also obtained for the MND and MYO groups. This is consistent with previous observations that AIC tends to overestimate the model order (Kashyap, 1980). The FPE criterion gave exactly identical results as the AIC criterion. AIC and FPE give equivalent results as N tends to infinitive (Marple, 1987). The normalized residual energy in AIC criterion generally was smaller compared to the MDL criterion, though it was nearly the same for all model orders selected. The AIC criterion was eventually used in the estimation of MUAPs AR spectra.

Plots displaying the linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$ and the AIC criterion as a function of the model order p for each MUAP of subject NOR1 are given in Figure 4.4. Similar graphs for the MND1 and MYO1 subjects are displayed in Figures 4.5 and 4.6 respectively. In these plots the AIC criterion is shown in dotted lines, whereas $\hat{\rho}_p$ is given in solid lines. The optimum model order is also given in the figure caption. From the above mentioned figures, it may be observed that both the linear prediction error variance and the AIC decrease as higher model orders are attained. When the optimum model order is reached the AIC gets its minimum value. From this point onwards the AIC criterion starts increasing again. In a number of MUAPs in the NOR group the linear prediction error variance reaches its minimum value at the same model order as the AIC criterion does. This is observed in Figure 4.4 in MUAPs 5, 6, 8, and 18. In these cases the optimum model order tracked by the AIC criterion coincides with the model order that minimizes the linear prediction error variance. In some other cases $\hat{\rho}_p$ is minimized at model orders slightly below or above optimum model order. This is illustrated in MUAPs 1, 2, 3, 9, 11, 13, 16, and 20, Figure 4.4. In several other cases the linear prediction error variance decreases monotonically with increasing model orders. This is shown in MUAPs 4, 7, 10, 12, 14, 15, 17, and 19, Figure 4.4. In these cases much higher model orders, sometimes even higher than 20, are required to represent the AR model. This monotonous change in values of the linear prediction error variance justifies the proper selection of the model order by the AIC criterion. In the MND and MYO groups similar findings were realized as shown in Figures 4.5 and 4.6 respectively.

4.2.3 *Model validity*

Figures 4.7, 4.8, and 4.9 show the residuals periodograms for NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. The normalized residuals periodogram of each MUAP, expressed in dB, is plotted as a function of frequency. On each individual graph the optimum model order is given. In all residuals periodograms, it may be observed that the spectrum is flat or slightly varying up and down. Visual inspection of the plots suggests that the residuals periodogram generally resembles the spectrum of a white noise sequence. This indicates that the AR model represents adequately the MUAP data.

Figures 4.10, 4.11, and 4.12 give the normalized cumulative residuals periodograms for NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. The vertical axis represents normalized cumulative residuals power values, whereas the horizontal axis displays normalized frequency values. Residuals power values are normalized with maximum residuals power in each MUAP. Frequency values are normalized to the sampling frequency that is 10kHz. The optimum model order is also shown in each graph. All normalized cumulative residuals periodograms yielded almost a straight line with a slope of two passing through the origin. Slight deviations from this line are allowed

as documented in Box and Jenkins, 1976. Results showed that all model orders produced white noise residuals using the cumulative residuals periodogram test.

The adequacy of the AR model was also checked by the portmanteau test statistic Q applied on the residuals. This was suggested by Hefftner et al, 1988. Tables 4.11, 4.12, and 4.13 give the results of the above statistic for the MUAPs recorded from NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. The Q statistic adds the autocorrelations of the residuals for the first m lags multiplied by the number of residuals N . m was chosen to be 24. Q is considered to have approximately a chi-square distribution $\chi_{\alpha, v}^2$ if the model is appropriate. α was chosen to be 0,05, and v gives the degrees of freedom. v is equal to $(m-p)$. The Q statistic compensates for the model estimation by reducing the degrees of freedom by the number of the estimated parameters p . Q values are then compared to $\chi_{0,05, 24-p}^2$ values in the chi-square distribution table. p is the optimal model order, that might be different in each MUAP. Results from the above referred tables illustrate that Q is smaller than $\chi_{0,05, 24-p}^2$ in all MUAPs suggesting that the hypothesis of model adequacy can be accepted.

4.3 AR spectrum

As it was previously mentioned the optimum AR model order was estimated using the AIC criterion, and the AR parameters were estimated using the modified covariance method. The mean value was removed from the data sequence of 256 points of each MUAP before processing the signal in the frequency domain. The data sequence was also zero augmented from $p+1$ to $4N$ data points before computing the AR power spectrum. N to $4N-1$ zero values were also added to the MUAP data sequence before computing the FFT power spectrum. The FFT and AR spectra for the NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects are displayed in Figures 4.13, 4.14, and 4.15 respectively. On the y-axis the normalized power of each MUAP expressed in dB is given, whereas on the x-axis the frequency in kHz is displayed. AR spectra are shown in dotted lines and FFT spectra in solid lines. Model order p and potential number are also given in every plot. The power is normalized with the maximum power value present in each MUAP.

Generally, the AR spectra followed closely the FFT spectra or they formed the envelope of their partner particularly when the FFT spectra were spiky. In a limited number of MUAPs in the NOR1 subject the AR spectra tracked exactly the FFT spectra or roughly coincided with them. In the case of MND1 and MYO1 subjects, the AR spectra mostly formed the envelope of the FFT spectra which were noisy in nature. Power plots also showed that the AR spectra tended to

approach the FFT spectra of spiky character at higher model orders.

4.4 AR spectral measures

Various frequency and power measures were determined from the AR model power spectrum of each MUAP. The mean (μ), median, standard deviation (σ), lower quartile (Q_1), upper quartile (Q_3), and semi-interquartile range (SIQR) for the frequency and power measures of the NOR group are given in Tables 4.14 and 4.15 respectively. The median splits the data in half, and the quartiles Q_1 and Q_3 split each half once more. The semi-interquartile range is given as $SIQR = (Q_3 - Q_1)/2$. The above statistics are also given for the MND and MYO groups. The MND statistics for the frequency and power measures are provided in Tables 4.16 and 4.17 respectively. Finally, the MYO statistics for the frequency and power measures are tabulated in Tables 4.18 and 4.19 respectively. Frequency parameters determined were the following: centre frequency, median frequency, peak power frequency, upper and lower cut-off frequencies, bandwidth, quality factor, and frequencies at power levels of -5, -10, -15, -20, and -25dB. Power parameters determined were the following: moments of order 0, 1, and 2, and power levels at 100, 200, 300, 500, 750, 1000, 1250, 1500, 2000, and 2500Hz.

In the case of the MYO group all frequency parameters are greater compared to the respective values of frequency parameters in the NOR group. Furthermore, the BW in the MYO group is higher than in the NOR group. Specifically, the BW in the MYO group is 767Hz and in the NOR group 525Hz. Also, the power level of all frequency parameters in myopathy group is larger than in the NOR group. All the above show that the power spectrum in the case of myopathies is displayed towards higher frequencies with the power content in the high frequency components being larger than normal.

In case of the MND group the power spectrum is shifted towards lower frequencies as expected. This is confirmed with all frequency parameters being smaller than normal. The only exception is the frequency F_l that gives the lower -3dB point at 62Hz in the case of the MND group and at 35Hz in the NOR group. Also the peak power frequency F_0 in the MND group approaches that of the NOR group. Frequency F_0 in the MND group is 213Hz, whereas F_0 in the NOR group is 215Hz. Bandwidth BW also supports the statement that the power spectrum in the case of the MND group is displaced towards lower frequencies. BW in the MND group is 381Hz, whereas in the NOR group is 525Hz. The power content of all frequency components in the MND group is smaller than the NOR group.

Figure 4.16 also clearly shows the displacement of power spectrum towards higher frequencies in

case of myopathies and the shift of the power spectrum towards lower frequencies in case of neuropathies compared to the power spectrum of normal individuals. Figures 4.16 gives the AR power spectra of subjects NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 averaged over twenty MUAPs.

Spectral moment M_0 is actually the average power of the spectrum. Spectral moment M_0 is found to be bigger in the MYO group than the NOR group. M_0 in the MYO group is $29,70 \mu V^2$ and in the NOR group is $20,71 \mu V^2$. This is as expected because as mentioned earlier all typical frequency parameters computed in the MYO group were found to be of greater power than the respective frequencies in the NOR group. This is also justified by the value of the CF . CF or mean frequency is the frequency corresponding to the mean power of the spectrum. CF in MYO group is 755Hz which is close to 750Hz . Also CF in the NOR group is 522Hz which is very near to 500Hz . Power P_{750} in the MYO group is $-5,08\text{dB}$ which is greater than P_{500} in the NOR group which is $-5,68\text{dB}$. In case of the NOR group the actual power level at the CF of 522Hz is expected to be even smaller than $-5,68\text{dB}$.

Following a similar approach, it may be justified that M_0 in the MND group is smaller than M_0 in the NOR group. Actual values of M_0 in the MND and NOR groups are $15,30 \mu V^2$ and $20,71 \mu V^2$ respectively. Mostly frequencies in the MND group are lower and of smaller power content than the NOR group. Additionally, CF in the MND group is 447Hz and the power level at this frequency is near to $-7,95\text{dB}$. On the other hand, CF in the NOR group is 522Hz , and its power level is close to $-5,68\text{dB}$. Since CF is the frequency at the mean power, it follows from above that M_0 or mean power is greater in the NOR group than the MND group.

Spectral moments M_1 and M_2 represent the area of the power spectrum after being weighted by frequency raised to the power of one and two respectively (as illustrated in Equation 3.32). Thus, since all the frequency parameters in the MYO group were found of greater value and of higher power level, it follows that M_1 and M_2 in the MYO group would be greater than M_1 and M_2 in the NOR group. This is true since M_1 and M_2 are $27,68 \mu V^2/s*10^3$ and $45,41 \mu V^2/s^2*10^6$ in the MYO group respectively and $15,34 \mu V^2/s*10^3$ and $24,52 \mu V^2/s^2*10^6$ respectively in the NOR group. A similar justification is valid for M_1 and M_2 of the MND group when compared to the NOR group. M_1 and M_2 were found to be $9,54 \mu V^2/s*10^3$ and $14,12 \mu V^2/s^2*10^6$ respectively in the MND group, whereas M_1 and M_2 in the NOR group were $15,34 \mu V^2/s*10^3$ and $24,52 \mu V^2/s^2*10^6$ respectively.

4.5 AR coefficients, model order p , and linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$

In this work the AIC was used to track the optimum model order p for orders in the range 2 to

20. The AR coefficients were then estimated by the modified covariance method for the model order selected. Tables 4.20, 4.21, and 4.22 give the group statistics of model order p , linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$, and AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups respectively. The mean and standard deviation values of the model order p are $6,08 \pm 3,01$ for the NOR group, $7,67 \pm 4,19$ for the MND group, and $5,98 \pm 3,28$ for the MYO group. The results above suggested that twelve AR coefficients were adequate for modeling all disease groups. Results also showed that higher model orders were needed for the MND group compared to the NOR group due to the increased complexity of MUAPs shape in the MND subjects. On the contrary, model orders in the MYO group were lower in relation to model orders of the NOR group. This is true since MUAPs in the MYO subjects are characterized by their simple shape. Finally, model order p as well as the AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} were used as diagnostic features for discriminating the three disease groups.

In the NOR group, the mean linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$ is 963,32, and the mean model order is 6,08. In the MND group, $\hat{\rho}_p$ is 866,76 corresponding to a mean model order of 7,67. This is justified since $\hat{\rho}_p$ is expected to decrease with increasing model orders. However, $\hat{\rho}_p$ in the MYO group is smaller compared to $\hat{\rho}_p$ in the NOR group though the mean model order value is lower. Additionally, the standard deviation values of linear prediction error variance in all groups are very high compared to their means. This suggests that $\hat{\rho}_p$ cannot be used for the diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders.

4.6 Cepstral coefficients

Twelve cepstral coefficients were directly derived from the AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} using Equation 3.41. The statistics of the twelve cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups are tabulated in Tables 4.23, 4.24, and 4.25 respectively. Cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} were also used for differentiating nerve and muscle pathology.

4.7 Time domain and AR spectral parameters

4.7.1 Univariate statistical analysis

One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out for the following feature sets: i) time parameters duration, spike duration, amplitude, and number of turns, ii) frequency parameters centre frequency, median frequency, peak power frequency, bandwidth, quality factor, and spectral moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 , and iii) model order p . Results are outlined in Table 4.26. As given

in Table 4.26, the hypothesis that parameter means are equal is not correct at a significance level of $\alpha=0,05$ for all parameters. t-test analysis was also carried out between the NOR-MND, NOR-MYO, and MND-MYO groups. In the NOR-MND group, there is no significant difference in peak power frequency F_0 . In the NOR-MYO group, no significant difference exists in the amplitude and model order. Finally, in the MND-MYO group significant difference exists in all parameters except from quality factor.

Assumptions for ANOVA analysis to be valid are given in Table 4.26. Assumptions number 3 and 4 require that samples are normally distributed within each group, and that homogeneity exists between groups. These assumptions may be validated for the MUAPs under investigation. However, the assumption of normality for each parameter in each group is violated as demonstrated by histograms pictured in Figures 4.17 to 4.19.

Histograms of MUAP parameters duration, spike duration, and amplitude for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups are given in Figure 4.17. Distribution of polyphasic MUAPs is marked with crossed bars. Histograms clearly illustrate that MUAPs in MND are characterised by longer duration, larger number of polyphasic MUAPs, and greater amplitude compared to NOR MUAPs. In opposition to MUAPs in MND, MUAPs in MYO are shorter in length and of smaller amplitude. Moreover, the incidence of polyphasic potentials is also reduced.

Histograms of median frequency, quality factor, model order, and moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 , are given in Figures 4.18 and 4.19. Histograms in Figure 4.18 show that the median frequency is shifted towards higher frequencies in the MYO group compared to the NOR group. In the case of the MND group the opposite is valid for the median frequency. Histograms of model order in Figure 4.18 indicate that higher model orders are obtained for the MND group compared to the NOR group. This is justified since MND MUAPs are more complex than normal MUAPs. MYO MUAPs on the other hand are of simpler shape. Thus, lower model orders are required to model MUAPs recorded from myopathy subjects. Furthermore, histograms in Figure 4.19 show that moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 are higher in MYO group and lower in the MND group compared to the NOR group.

4.7.2 *Multivariate statistical analysis*

Correlation analysis was also carried out between various selected time parameters and parameters extracted from the AR power spectra. Correlation analysis results are tabulated in Table 4.27. Results in Table 4.27 show that time parameters are not strongly correlated with the rest of the features. High correlation exists between spectral moments M_0 , M_1 , M_2 , and frequency parameters

CF, *FMED*, and *BW*. The remaining parameters are not highly correlated between each other or with the above forementioned parameters. Correlation is considered to be weak if $0 \leq |\rho_{xy}| \leq 0,5$, moderate if $0,5 < |\rho_{xy}| < 0,8$, and strong if $0,8 \leq |\rho_{xy}| \leq 1$, where ρ_{xy} is the sample correlation coefficient (Devore, 1982).

The final feature set consists of the following parameters: duration, spike duration, amplitude, median frequency, moment M_2 , quality factor, and model order. Number of turns though not highly correlated with any of the above features was finally removed so as to have a reasonable number of time parameters in the final feature set. Additionally, M_2 though is highly correlated with *FMED*, was included in the feature selection analysis aiming at diversity. Peak power frequency F_0 is moderately correlated with the rest of the AR spectral measures and was finally dropped.

Correlation analysis was also carried out between power and frequency measures but results are not presented in this work. It was found that most of the power parameters P_{100} , P_{200} , P_{300} , P_{500} , P_{750} , P_{1000} , P_{1250} , P_{1500} , P_{2000} , P_{2500} and frequency parameters F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , F_{10} , F_{15} , F_{20} , and F_{25} were moderately to highly correlated with spectral moments M_0 , M_1 , M_2 , *CF*, *FMED*, F_0 and *BW* and were eventually considered as redundant.

4.8 Feature selection analysis

Univariate and multivariate analysis

Feature selection analysis results are listed in Table 4.28. Results showed that duration is the best discriminative feature among time parameters. *FMED* is the best feature among AR spectral measures. Model order p was ranked among the poorest classification features in the univariate method, whereas the M-Covar criterion classified it as the third best discriminative feature among all features studied.

4.9 Cluster analysis

4.9.1 K-means nearest neighbour classifier

Results of the cluster analysis performed by the K-means nearest neighbour classifier are summarised in Table 4.29. Data from the first eight subjects from each group was used to carry out the cluster analysis; NOR1 to NOR8 from the NOR group, MND1 to MND8 from the MND group, and MYO1 to MYO8 from the MYO group. The rest of the subjects from each group were used to evaluate the performance of the K-means models; NOR9 to NOR12 from the NOR group, MND9 to MND15 from the MND group, and MYO9 to MYO13 from the MYO group. The value of K which determines the number of clusters was chosen to be 3 as the number of classes

of diseases, and the number of iterations for all features sets was 50.

As shown in Table 4.29 different groups of features were inputted to the K-means algorithm. Their data was first standardized, and then the cluster analysis was carried out. The sample mean was calculated and subtracted from each feature value, and then the difference was divided by the sample standard deviation. The standardized values have mean 0 and standard deviation 1. Results showed that the best diagnostic performance for both the training and evaluation sets was obtained for the time parameters feature set which includes duration, spike duration, phases, and amplitude. The above group of features gave 67% CCs for the training set and 81% CCs for the evaluation set. In model 5, model order p gave the next highest classification performance in the training set with 63% CCs, whereas its diagnostic yield was reduced to 56% in the evaluation set. Feature sets c_1 to c_5 and c_1 to c_{12} in the training set were ranked higher than the AR spectral parameters and the AR coefficients. The AR spectral parameters and AR coefficients in the training set gave similar results. On the other hand, in the evaluation set the feature sets of AR spectral parameters, AR coefficients α_1 to α_5 , and cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 gave equivalent results. Poorer performance was obtained with feature sets α_1 to α_{12} and c_1 to c_{12} .

4.9.2 Euclidean distance classifier

The Euclidean distance classifier evaluated the classification performance of the same group of feature sets as in the case of the K-means nearest neighbour classifier for both the training and the evaluation sets. Standardized data was also used in this analysis. Results given by the Euclidean distance classifier are shown in Table 4.30.

In model 7, duration, spike duration, phases, and amplitude gave the highest diagnostic yield for the training set with 92% CCs. The same model gave only 50% CCs for the evaluation set. In the training set, the AR spectral parameters gave 71% CCs and in the evaluation set 75% CCs. Model order p , AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} , and cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 and c_1 to c_{12} gave identical results in the training set with 67% CCs. In the evaluation set, the cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 were ranked higher than model order p , cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} , and AR coefficients with 69% CCs. AR coefficients α_1 to α_5 gave the poorest classification performance for both the training and evaluation sets.

Table 4.1 Number of subjects examined in each group.

Group	No. of subjects	No. of MUAPs
Normal	12	240
Motor Neurone Disease	15	300
Myopathy	13	260

Table 4.2 MUAP statistics from the brachial biceps muscle for the NOR group (12 subjects, no. of MUAPs = 240).

	Dur ms	Area mVms	SpDur ms	SpArea mVms	Ph	T	Amp mV
mn	10,15	0,39	5,72	0,26	2,53	2,75	0,40
median	10,09	0,35	5,13	0,23	2,00	2,67	0,32
<i>s</i>	2,80	0,20	2,44	0,13	0,74	0,84	0,32
Q ₁	8,02	0,25	3,91	0,16	2,00	2,20	0,19
Q ₃	12,11	0,49	7,37	0,32	3,00	3,00	0,49
SIQR	2,05	0,12	1,73	0,08	0,50	0,40	0,15

Table 4.3 MUAP statistics from the brachial biceps muscle for the MND group (15 subjects, no. of MUAPs = 300).

	Dur ms	Area mVms	SpDur ms	SpArea mVms	Ph	T	Amp mV
mn	12,84	0,73	6,75	0,46	3,60	4,01	0,54
median	12,90	0,63	5,90	0,39	3,00	3,33	0,46
<i>s</i>	3,60	0,46	3,73	0,31	1,60	2,13	0,37
Q ₁	10,04	0,40	3,95	0,26	3,00	2,50	0,27
Q ₃	15,30	0,93	8,45	0,58	4,00	5,00	0,67
SIQR	2,63	0,27	2,25	0,16	0,50	1,25	0,20

Table 4.4 MUAP statistics from the brachial biceps muscle for the MYO group (13 subjects, no. of MUAPs = 260).

	Dur ms	Area mVms	SpDur ms	SpArea mVms	Ph	T	Amp mV
mn	7,42	0,25	4,75	0,18	2,70	3,51	0,36
median	7,23	0,22	4,60	0,15	2,00	3,14	0,27
<i>s</i>	2,26	0,18	1,82	0,12	0,98	1,35	0,30
Q ₁	5,78	0,13	3,62	0,10	2,00	2,56	0,16
Q ₃	8,74	0,32	5,75	0,22	3,00	4,37	0,45
SIQR	1,48	0,10	1,07	0,06	0,50	0,91	0,15

Table 4.5 Results of the stationarity test for each NOR subject. Percentage of potentials in each subject that passed the stationarity test is tabulated for a level of significance of $\alpha = 0,05$.

Subject No.	$\bar{x}$ statistic		<i>s</i> statistic	
	Run-test (%)	Reverse arrangements test (%)	Run-test (%)	Reverse arrangements test (%)
NOR1	90	100	85	90
NOR2	90	95	65	85
NOR3	90	95	50	90
NOR4	75	95	70	100
NOR5	100	95	80	90
NOR6	100	100	95	85
NOR7	90	95	80	90
NOR8	100	100	65	85
NOR9	90	100	70	65
NOR10	95	85	90	85
NOR11	85	95	75	95
NOR12	100	95	75	80
mn	92	96	75	87

Table 4.6 Results of the stationarity test for each MND subject. Percentage of potentials in each subject that passed the stationarity test is tabulated for a level of significance of $\alpha = 0,05$.

Subject No.	$\bar{x}$ statistic		s statistic	
	Run-test (%)	Reverse arrangements test (%)	Run-test (%)	Reverse arrangements test (%)
MND1	90	100	80	95
MND2	95	100	50	80
MND3	95	95	70	80
MND4	95	95	40	40
MND5	90	100	90	95
MND6	95	100	60	90
MND7	95	95	70	100
MND8	80	95	55	70
MND9	95	100	50	90
MND10	95	95	45	55
MND11	90	95	75	85
MND12	95	95	85	80
MND13	85	95	80	90
MND14	85	90	75	90
MND15	95	100	45	75
mn	92	97	65	81

Table 4.7 Results of the stationarity test for each MYO subject. Percentage of potentials in each subject that passed the stationarity test is tabulated for a level of significance of $\alpha = 0,05$.

Subject No.	$\bar{x}$ statistic		s statistic	
	Run-test (%)	Reverse arrangements test (%)	Run-test (%)	Reverse arrangements test (%)
MYO1	95	95	85	100
MYO2	85	70	90	100
MYO3	95	85	80	90
MYO4	95	95	55	85
MYO5	90	75	80	90
MYO6	80	85	60	75
MYO7	90	80	90	85
MYO8	90	95	80	90
MYO9	90	90	85	90
MYO10	90	95	85	95
MYO11	95	95	85	85
MYO12	90	85	95	90
MYO13	70	75	90	90
mn	89	86	82	90

Table 4.8 Mean and standard deviation values of model order p and normalized residual energy e_{NORM} using AIC, FPE, and MDL criteria for the NOR group.

Subject No.	AIC & FPE						MDL					
	p			e_{NORM}			p			e_{NORM}		
	mn	s		mn	s		mn	s		mn	s	
NOR1	5,250	2,023	0,212	0,233	3,700	1,455	0,215	0,237				
NOR2	5,650	2,978	0,222	0,225	3,700	1,490	0,224	0,225				
NOR3	6,500	3,154	0,033	0,069	4,450	0,999	0,033	0,069				
NOR4	5,500	2,800	0,102	0,166	4,100	1,804	0,104	0,166				
NOR5	6,800	4,124	0,067	0,071	4,150	1,981	0,068	0,072				
NOR6	5,900	2,125	0,072	0,173	3,650	1,268	0,072	0,172				
NOR7	5,350	2,033	0,130	0,167	4,600	1,667	0,132	0,169				
NOR8	5,800	2,546	0,058	0,083	3,550	0,999	0,058	0,083				
NOR9	7,050	3,154	0,124	0,157	4,450	1,701	0,127	0,158				
NOR10	5,300	2,203	0,172	0,181	4,200	1,824	0,175	0,182				
NOR11	5,900	3,093	0,158	0,172	4,450	1,638	0,160	0,172				
NOR12	8,000	4,292	0,069	0,078	4,400	1,603	0,072	0,080				
mn	6,083			0,118			4,117			0,120		
s	3,009			0,166			1,569			0,167		

Table 4.9 Mean and standard deviation values of model order p and normalized residual energy e_{NORM} using AIC, FPE, and MDL criteria for the MND group.

Subject No.	AIC & FPE						MDL					
	p		e_{NORM}		p		e_{NORM}		p		e_{NORM}	
	mn	s	mn	s	mn	s	mn	s	mn	s	mn	s
MND1	9,900	4,667	0,124	0,060	6,200	2,441	0,132	0,063				
MND2	10,400	5,433	0,031	0,053	4,650	2,498	0,036	0,066				
MND3	7,750	4,363	0,046	0,073	4,250	1,552	0,050	0,079				
MND4	8,100	4,855	0,065	0,094	5,200	2,118	0,068	0,099				
MND5	5,850	3,870	0,099	0,179	3,650	1,496	0,100	0,179				
MND6	7,500	3,052	0,091	0,116	4,650	2,390	0,098	0,130				
MND7	5,150	2,390	0,052	0,047	4,000	1,338	0,053	0,047				
MND8	8,900	4,610	0,067	0,081	4,600	2,210	0,075	0,094				
MND9	7,600	4,535	0,034	0,060	5,050	2,328	0,034	0,060				
MND10	7,350	4,120	0,120	0,080	5,500	2,328	0,123	0,081				
MND11	6,400	3,169	0,159	0,214	3,700	1,342	0,163	0,219				
MND12	8,200	4,034	0,053	0,097	5,500	2,565	0,054	0,097				
MND13	8,050	3,441	0,088	0,176	4,950	2,188	0,091	0,176				
MND14	5,650	2,907	0,210	0,213	3,950	1,317	0,214	0,213				
MND15	8,250	3,878	0,042	0,039	5,350	1,981	0,045	0,042				
mn	7,670		0,085		4,747		0,089					
s	4,190		0,127		2,132		0,131					

Table 4.10 Mean and standard deviation values of model order p and normalized residual energy e_{NORM} using AIC, FPE, and MDL criteria for the MYO group.

Subject No.	AIC & FPE						MDL					
	p			e_{NORM}			p			e_{NORM}		
	mn	s		mn	s		mn	s		mn	s	
MYO1	5,000	2,513		0,174	0,119		3,800	1,152		0,176	0,119	
MYO2	3,650	1,137		0,412	0,242		2,950	0,887		0,416	0,245	
MYO3	6,600	4,044		0,097	0,079		5,600	3,789		0,101	0,089	
MYO4	6,850	4,221		0,100	0,124		4,700	1,809		0,102	0,125	
MYO5	6,500	2,743		0,125	0,165		4,200	1,795		0,127	0,165	
MYO6	5,300	1,809		0,144	0,107		4,300	1,218		0,147	0,112	
MYO7	6,300	2,793		0,200	0,165		4,450	1,638		0,209	0,172	
MYO8	7,550	3,677		0,078	0,088		4,250	1,251		0,081	0,093	
MYO9	5,550	2,259		0,159	0,117		4,400	1,231		0,161	0,117	
MYO10	6,400	3,267		0,126	0,096		3,600	0,940		0,128	0,096	
MYO11	4,900	2,614		0,288	0,231		3,750	1,888		0,293	0,235	
MYO12	6,200	4,275		0,201	0,098		3,850	1,755		0,208	0,099	
MYO13	7,000	4,255		0,231	0,128		4,550	2,089		0,239	0,133	
mn	5,985			0,179			4,185			0,184		
s	3,284			0,166			1,861			0,169		

Table 4.11 Results of the portmanteau test statistic of residuals for subject NOR1.

MUAP No.	p	Q	$\chi^2_{\alpha, v}^*$
1	10	0,229	23,685
2	3	0,370	32,670
3	4	0,095	31,410
4	9	0,084	24,996
5	5	0,324	30,143
6	7	0,218	27,587
7	6	0,286	28,869
8	7	0,220	27,587
9	3	0,059	32,670
10	6	0,057	28,869
11	3	0,016	32,670
12	5	0,158	30,143
13	5	0,037	30,143
14	4	0,233	31,410
15	4	0,226	31,410
16	3	0,023	32,670
17	5	0,174	30,143
18	7	0,324	27,587
19	6	0,060	28,869
20	3	0,216	32,670

*Significance level $\alpha=0,05$

v =degrees of freedom= $m-p$

m =number of residual autocorrelation lags=24

p =optimal model order

Table 4.12 Results of the portmanteau test statistic of residuals for subject MND1.

MUAP No.	p	Q	$\chi^2_{\alpha, v}^*$
1	17	2,171	14,067
2	7	0,167	27,587
3	5	0,094	30,143
4	17	1,023	14,067
5	10	1,950	23,685
6	9	0,373	24,996
7	12	0,178	21,026
8	11	0,132	22,362
9	18	0,423	12,592
10	5	0,101	30,143
11	6	0,350	28,869
12	14	0,216	18,307
13	8	0,237	26,296
14	5	0,115	30,143
15	6	0,285	28,869
16	6	0,201	28,869
17	11	2,343	22,362
18	5	0,314	30,143
19	8	0,800	26,296
20	18	0,901	12,592

*Significance level $\alpha=0,05$

v =degrees of freedom= $m-p$

m =number of residual autocorrelation lags=24

p =optimal model order

Table 4.13 Results of the portmanteau test statistic of residuals for subject MYO1.

MUAP No.	p	Q	$\chi^2_{\alpha, v}^*$
1	3	0,152	32,670
2	4	0,347	31,410
3	4	0,173	31,410
4	14	0,121	18,307
5	3	0,095	32,670
6	4	0,301	31,410
7	8	0,563	26,296
8	3	0,086	32,670
9	5	0,248	30,143
10	6	0,190	28,869
11	4	0,296	31,410
12	5	0,100	30,143
13	5	0,055	30,143
14	3	0,179	32,670
15	3	0,085	32,670
16	4	0,110	31,410
17	4	0,129	31,410
18	6	0,190	28,869
19	6	0,289	28,869
20	6	0,196	28,869

*Significance level $\alpha = 0,05$

v =degrees of freedom= $m-p$

m =number of residual autocorrelation lags=24

p =optimal model order

Table 4.14 Statistics of frequency measures for the NOR group (12 subjects, no. of MUAPs=240).

	CF Hz	FMED Hz	F ₀ Hz	F ₁ Hz	F ₂ Hz	BW Hz	Q	F ₅ Hz	F ₁₀ Hz	F ₁₅ Hz	F ₂₀ Hz	F ₂₅ Hz
mn	522	413	215	35	560	525	0,47	730	1196	1672	2163	2614
median	377	312	195	0	424	410	0,48	527	820	1260	1762	2231
s	332	285	278	104	428	432	0,57	574	913	1108	1257	1302
Q ₁	296	229	0	0	322	254	0,00	380	590	849	1196	1640
Q ₃	658	493	302	0	566	556	0,67	786	1523	2280	2910	3593
SIQR	181	132	151	0	122	151	0,34	203	467	716	857	977

Table 4.15 Statistics of power measures for the NOR group (12 subjects, no. of MUAPs=240).

	M ₀ μV ²	M ₁ μV ² /s*10 ³	M ₂ μV ² /s ² *10 ⁶	P ₁₀₀ dB	P ₂₀₀ dB	P ₃₀₀ dB	P ₅₀₀ dB	P ₇₅₀ dB	P ₁₀₀₀ dB	P ₁₂₅₀ dB	P ₁₅₀₀ dB	P ₂₀₀₀ dB	P ₂₅₀₀ dB
mn	20,71	15,34	24,52	-1,4	-1,1	-1,9	-5,7	-9,6	-12,6	-15,1	-17,5	-21,7	-25,4
median	16,18	6,09	4,53	-0,8	-0,7	-1,3	-4,6	-8,8	-12,0	-14,8	-17,5	-22,9	-27,1
s	15,02	23,06	51,95	1,5	1,2	2,1	4,5	6,5	7,9	9,2	10,2	10,9	11,0
Q ₁	11,34	3,09	1,77	-2,1	-1,6	-2,7	-8,3	-13,5	-17,5	-20,8	-23,1	-28,9	-33,3
Q ₃	24,00	16,55	19,38	-0,2	-0,2	-0,4	-2,2	-4,8	-6,3	-8,3	-9,7	-12,8	-16,6
SIQR	6,33	6,73	8,81	0,95	1,4	1,2	3,1	4,4	5,6	6,3	6,7	8,1	8,4

Table 4.16 Statistics of frequency measures for the MND group (15 subjects, no. of MUAPs=300).

	CF Hz	FMED Hz	F ₀ Hz	F ₁ Hz	F ₂ Hz	BW Hz	Q	F ₅ Hz	F ₁₀ Hz	F ₁₅ Hz	F ₂₀ Hz	F ₂₅ Hz
mn	446	339	213	61	442	381	0,71	536	853	1252	1760	2280
median	335	263	210	0	361	293	0,60	419	595	908	1401	2021
s	283	241	240	124	361	349	0,98	427	699	905	1100	1245
Q ₁	259	205	0	0	273	205	0	332	488	664	888	1191
Q ₃	561	356	283	117	449	419	1,04	527	849	1601	2431	3203
SIQR	151	76	142	59	88	107	0,52	98	181	469	772	1006

Table 4.17 Statistics of power measures for the MND group (15 subjects, no. of MUAPs=300).

	M ₀ μV ²	M ₁ μV ² /s*10 ³	M ₂ μV ² /s ² *10 ⁶	P ₁₀₀ dB	P ₂₀₀ dB	P ₃₀₀ dB	P ₅₀₀ dB	P ₇₅₀ dB	P ₁₀₀₀ dB	P ₁₂₅₀ dB	P ₁₅₀₀ dB	P ₂₀₀₀ dB	P ₂₅₀₀ dB
mn	15,30	9,54	14,12	-2,1	-1,6	-2,8	-8,0	-13,1	-16,5	-19,1	-21,1	-24,6	-28,1
median	12,11	4,14	2,92	-1,4	-0,9	-1,8	-7,6	-12,8	-15,9	-18,3	-20,6	-24,0	-28,0
s	11,80	17,59	39,70	2,0	1,9	2,8	5,0	7,2	8,8	10,0	10,6	10,9	10,8
Q ₁	9,0	2,38	1,13	-3,5	-2,5	-4,3	-10,5	-16,9	-22,1	-25,7	-28,1	-32,1	-35,8
Q ₃	16,6	8,63	10,10	-0,5	-0,3	-0,4	-4,7	-8,9	-10,6	-12,0	-13,3	-15,3	-19,2
SIQR	3,80	3,13	4,49	1,5	1,1	2,0	5,8	4,0	5,8	6,9	7,4	8,4	8,3

Table 4.18 Statistics of frequency measures for the MYO group (13 subjects, no. of MUAPs=260).

	CF Hz	FMED Hz	F_0 Hz	F_1 Hz	F_2 Hz	BW Hz	Q	F_5 Hz	F_{10} Hz	F_{15} Hz	F_{20} Hz	F_{25} Hz
mn	755	629	411	104	871	767	0,63	1109	1710	2278	2831	3449
median	726	595	371	0	796	639	0,57	967	1606	2177	2783	3452
s	355	344	389	200	549	539	0,78	677	953	1068	1150	1206
Q_1	464	346	0	0	410	341	0	546	913	1469	1899	2392
Q_3	961	805	635	141	1181	1109	0,81	1533	2285	2939	3662	4628
SIQR	249	230	318	71	386	384	0,41	494	686	735	882	1118

Table 4.19 Statistics of power measures for the MYO group (13 subjects, no. of MUAPs=260).

	M_0 μV^2	M_1 $\mu V^2/s*10^3$	M_2 $\mu V^2/s^2*10^6$	P_{100} dB	P_{200} dB	P_{300} dB	P_{500} dB	P_{750} dB	P_{1000} dB	P_{1250} dB	P_{1500} dB	P_{2000} dB	P_{2500} dB
mn	29,70	27,68	45,41	-2,3	-2,1	-2,1	-3,1	-5,1	-7,1	-8,9	-10,7	-14,8	-18,8
median	26,31	19,36	21,74	-1,4	-1,5	-1,5	-1,7	-2,9	-5,1	-6,9	-8,7	-12,9	-17,2
s	16,88	27,18	64,95	2,4	2,2	2,2	3,5	5,2	6,4	7,4	8,1	9,1	9,9
Q_1	17,15	8,17	6,83	-3,4	-3,1	-3,1	-4,6	-8,5	-10,6	-12,6	-15,3	-21,6	-25,7
Q_3	38,43	37,75	56,49	-0,4	-0,4	-0,5	-0,4	-0,8	-2,0	-3,4	-4,6	-7,5	-11,3
SIQR	10,64	14,79	24,83	1,5	1,4	1,3	2,1	3,9	4,3	4,6	5,4	7,1	7,2

Table 4.20 Statistics of model order p , linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$, and AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} for the NOR group (12 subjects, no. of MUAPs = 240)

	p	$\hat{\rho}_p$	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
mn	6,08	963,32	-1,668010	1,092608	-0,417521	0,210669	-0,130027
median	5,00	98,53	-1,719591	1,084760	-0,345115	0,182304	-0,044093
s	3,01	3593,13	0,420822	0,691752	0,641230	0,486064	0,371162
Q_1	4,00	36,16	-1,953687	0,529664	-0,777543	-0,093081	-0,255725
Q_3	8,00	444,63	-1,423594	1,577509	-0,046084	0,353903	0,106931
SIQR	6,00	204,24	0,265047	0,523923	0,365730	0,223492	0,181328

	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}	α_{11}	α_{12}
mn	0,113423	-0,091136	0,018550	0,017705	-0,000872	0,000612	-0,002984
median	0,003557	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
s	0,293977	0,234101	0,192322	0,182741	0,136583	0,093753	0,081842
Q_1	0,000000	-0,168219	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
Q_3	0,218075	0,000000	0,009873	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
SIQR	0,109038	0,084110	0,004937	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000

Table 4.21 Statistics of model order p , linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$, and AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} for the MND group (15 subjects, no. of MUAPs = 300)

	p	$\hat{\rho}_p$	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
mn	7,67	866,76	-1,723160	1,214877	-0,635927	0,339362	-0,165833
median	6,00	170,75	-1,765095	1,253220	-0,581629	0,284515	-0,123881
s	4,19	2409,31	0,439856	0,718538	0,671467	0,522950	0,417175
Q_1	4,00	69,47	-2,017852	0,713801	-1,039701	0,020028	-0,349999
Q_3	10,00	633,12	-1,454764	1,682230	-0,169344	0,615313	0,085009
SIQR	7,00	281,83	0,281544	0,484215	0,435179	0,297643	0,217504

	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}	α_{11}	α_{12}
mn	0,114510	-0,096369	0,079257	-0,045432	-0,005655	0,019720	-0,000086
median	0,044824	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
s	0,345164	0,296878	0,261214	0,237154	0,220224	0,188069	0,158873
Q_1	-0,083081	-0,222641	0,000000	-0,117532	-0,033553	0,000000	0,000000
Q_3	0,268699	0,020351	0,212844	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
SIQR	0,175890	0,121496	0,106422	0,058766	0,016777	0,000000	0,000000

Table 4.22 Statistics of model order p , linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$, and AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} for the MYO group (13 subjects, no. of MUAPs = 260)

	p	$\hat{\rho}_p$	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
mn	5,98	670,82	-1,579977	1,204518	-0,631906	0,330669	-0,192223
median	5,00	133,14	-1,615372	1,218831	-0,559983	0,200152	-0,107416
s	3,28	1954,45	0,415501	0,589850	0,571509	0,463620	0,365019
Q_1	4,00	54,66	-1,862010	0,802557	-0,935783	0,045866	-0,410002
Q_3	7,00	473,19	-1,308692	1,570647	-0,256693	0,642146	0,000000
SIQR	5,50	209,27	0,276659	0,384045	0,339545	0,298140	0,205001

	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}	α_{11}	α_{12}
mn	0,105285	-0,060685	0,046554	-0,020974	0,013743	-0,008572	0,010371
median	0,059254	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
s	0,271477	0,219653	0,194694	0,158845	0,117944	0,105679	0,097425
Q_1	0,000000	-0,129523	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
Q_3	0,195156	0,000000	0,121233	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000
SIQR	0,097578	0,064762	0,060617	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000	0,000000

Table 4.23 Statistics of cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} for the NOR group (12 subjects, no. of MUAFs = 240).

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5	c_6	c_7	c_8	c_9	c_{10}	c_{11}	c_{12}
mn	1,668010	0,386697	0,200811	0,123910	0,101349	0,049142	0,040310	0,037209	0,020981	0,023168	0,024834	0,040019
median	1,719591	0,383801	0,155541	0,113517	0,087018	0,042968	0,030959	0,019494	0,003231	0,005339	-0,002657	-0,001916
s	0,420822	0,431402	0,215739	0,151817	0,118718	0,116364	0,137804	0,144269	0,179839	0,212216	0,291446	0,366013
Q_1	1,423594	0,010004	0,052913	0,017324	0,024866	-0,011383	-0,016973	-0,011839	-0,035064	-0,029003	-0,035338	-0,024808
Q_3	1,953687	0,725751	0,311142	0,204845	0,166685	0,108519	0,082584	0,068045	0,042888	0,036866	0,024827	0,023999
SIQR	0,265047	0,357874	0,129115	0,093761	0,070910	0,059951	0,049779	0,039942	0,077952	0,032935	0,030083	0,024404

Table 4.24 Statistics of cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} for the MND group (15 subjects, no. of MUAFs=300).

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5	c_6	c_7	c_8	c_9	c_{10}	c_{11}	c_{12}
mn	1,723160	0,366177	0,304737	0,189913	0,131919	0,074525	0,057157	0,022531	0,007635	0,025021	0,017820	0,027882
median	1,765095	0,342317	0,266332	0,162967	0,121198	0,067167	0,046255	0,013457	-0,001788	0,006569	-0,004368	-0,003509
s	0,439856	0,421948	0,243998	0,180572	0,151253	0,146572	0,177345	0,199724	0,225184	0,261658	0,308422	0,386145
Q_1	1,454764	0,036537	0,127453	0,064064	0,017877	-0,002103	-0,008670	-0,044814	-0,057385	-0,041252	-0,047779	-0,051380
Q_3	2,017852	0,673020	0,468979	0,307832	0,229357	0,145389	0,123869	0,072366	0,052739	0,056181	0,039614	0,027257
SIQR	0,281544	0,318242	0,170763	0,121884	0,105740	0,073746	0,066270	0,060253	0,055062	0,048717	0,043697	0,039319

Table 4.25 Statistics of cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} for the MYO group (13 subjects, no. of MUAPs=260).

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5	c_6	c_7	c_8	c_9	c_{10}	c_{11}	c_{12}
mn	1,579977	0,129635	0,080628	0,014515	0,021473	0,006215	-0,003685	-0,012868	-0,005609	0,005091	0,017915	0,019449
median	1,615372	0,040225	0,058798	0,001663	-0,003476	-0,002926	-0,006838	-0,007057	-0,004871	-0,001365	0,000841	0,001358
s	0,415501	0,384323	0,180367	0,128453	0,132818	0,124227	0,119866	0,109165	0,109275	0,134606	0,138857	0,131812
Q_1	1,308692	-0,140183	-0,046616	-0,064017	-0,049957	-0,055779	-0,051304	-0,062060	-0,050031	-0,037253	-0,023963	-0,013887
Q_3	1,862010	0,412813	0,183591	0,085647	0,078654	0,060124	0,043905	0,026644	0,020188	0,027779	0,027363	0,022551
SIQR	0,276659	0,276498	0,115104	0,074832	0,064306	0,057952	0,047605	0,044362	0,035110	0,032516	0,025663	0,018219

Table 4.26 One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) of various selected time and AR spectral parameters.

	$H_0 : \mu_{NOR} = \mu_{MND} = \mu_{MYO}$			
	Significant difference	Pair comparisons (t-tests)		
		NOR-MND*	NOR-MYO*	MND-MYO*
<i>Dur</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>SpDur</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Amp</i>	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
<i>T</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>M₀</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>M₁</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>M₂</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>CF</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>FMED</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>F₀</i>	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
<i>BW</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Q</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
<i>p</i>	Yes	Yes	No	Yes

*Significant difference at level $\alpha=0,05$

Assumptions:

1. Random samples.
2. Independent Groups.
3. Normal Distributions ($N(\mu, \sigma^2)$).
4. Homogeneity ($\sigma^2_{NOR} = \sigma^2_{MND} = \sigma^2_{MYO}$).

Table 4.27 Correlation matrix between various selected time and AR spectral parameters for 12 NOR, 15 MND, and 13 MYO subjects (no. of MUAPs=800).

	Dur	SpDur	Amp	T	M_0	M_1	M_2	CF	FMED	F_0	BW	Q	p
Dur	1,000												
SpDur	0,474	1,000											
Amp	0,402	0,172	1,000										
T	0,308	0,352	0,200	1,000									
M_0	-0,228	-0,076	0,124	0,020	1,000								
M_1	-0,182	-0,067	0,163	0,026	0,952	1,000							
M_2	-0,142	-0,054	0,170	0,018	0,877	0,978	1,000						
CF	-0,224	-0,051	0,182	0,128	0,888	0,899	0,844	1,000					
FMED	-0,229	-0,087	0,172	0,090	0,905	0,916	0,853	0,959	1,000				
F_0	-0,165	-0,119	0,122	0,028	0,607	0,648	0,601	0,577	0,692	1,000			
BW	-0,210	-0,092	0,110	-0,020	0,956	0,901	0,827	0,760	0,807	0,633	1,000		
Q	0,032	-0,002	0,026	0,084	-0,140	-0,063	-0,054	-0,015	0,086	0,431	-0,157	1,000	
p	0,157	0,103	0,091	0,146	-0,339	-0,264	-0,241	-0,183	-0,157	-0,010	-0,366	0,439	1,000

Table 4.28 Feature selection using the univariate and the multiple covariance analysis methods.

Feature No.	Feature	Univar criterion	Feature	M-Covar criterion
1	Dur	0,325	<i>FMED</i>	25,706
2	<i>FMED</i>	-1,749	Dur	12,381
3	SpDur	-3,284	<i>p</i>	5,424
4	M_2	-3,520	Amp	2,188
5	Amp	-8,363	M_2	1,669
6	<i>Q</i>	-9,497	<i>Q</i>	1,198
7	<i>p</i>	-114,172	SpDur	0,096

Table 4.29 K-means cluster analysis performance.

Model	Feature set	Training set							Evaluation set						
		% CCs	% FPs	% FNs	% SE	% SP	% PPV	% NPV	% CCs	% FPs	% FNs	% SE	% SP	% PPV	% NPV
1	$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5$	42	88	44	56	12	56	13	44	100	42	58	0	64	0
2	$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7, \alpha_8, \alpha_9, \alpha_{10}, \alpha_{11}, \alpha_{12}$	42	0	88	12	100	100	36	31	0	92	8	100	100	27
3	c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5	46	63	50	50	37	62	27	44	50	58	42	50	71	22
4	$c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6, c_7, c_8, c_9, c_{10}, c_{11}, c_{12}$	54	0	69	31	100	100	42	38	25	75	25	75	75	25
5	P	63	0	56	44	100	100	47	56	25	50	50	75	86	33
6	$M_\phi, M, M_2, CF, FMED, F_\phi, BW, Q$	42	88	44	56	12	56	13	44	50	58	42	50	71	36
7	Dur, SpDur, Ph, Amp	67	0	50	50	100	100	50	81	0	25	75	100	100	57

K = number of clusters = 3

Number of iterations for all group of features = 50

Table 4.30 Performance of Euclidean distance classifier.

Model	Feature set	Training set							Evaluation set						
		% CCs	% FPs	% FNs	% SE	% SP	% PPV	% NPV	% CCs	% FPs	% FNs	% SE	% SP	% PPV	% NPV
1	$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5$	50	25	63	37	75	75	38	25	83	17	50	50	50	17
2	$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7, \alpha_8, \alpha_9, \alpha_{10}, \alpha_{11}, \alpha_{12}$	67	13	44	56	87	90	50	50	81	19	50	60	13	
3	c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5	67	50	25	75	50	75	50	69	42	58	100	100	44	
4	$c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6, c_7, c_8, c_9, c_{10}, c_{11}, c_{12}$	67	25	38	62	75	83	50	31	83	17	75	67	23	
5	p	67	25	38	62	75	83	50	56	56	44	50	78	18	
6	$M_0, M_1, M_2, CF, FMED, F_0, BW, Q$	71	38	25	75	62	80	56	75	33	67	100	100	50	
7	Dur, SpDur, Ph, Amp	92	0	13	87	100	100	80	50	69	31	75	83	21	

Figure 4.3 MUAPs from the brachial biceps muscle of subject MYO1.

Figure 4.4 Linear prediction error variance $\hat{p}_p$ and AIC criterion as a function of model order p for subject NOR1. $\hat{p}_p$ is shown in solid lines and AIC in dotted lines.

Figure 4.5 Linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$ and AIC criterion as a function of model order p for subject MND1. $\hat{\rho}_p$ is shown in solid lines and AIC in dotted lines.

Figure 4.6 Linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$ and AIC criterion as a function of model order p for subject MYO1. $\hat{\rho}_p$ is shown in solid lines and AIC in dotted lines.

Figure 4.7 Normalized residuals periodogram for subject NORI.

Figure 4.8 Normalized residuals periodogram for subject MND1.

Figure 4.9 Normalized residuals periodogram for subject MYO1.

Figure 4.10 Normalized cumulative residuals periodogram for subject NORI.

Figure 4.11 Normalized cumulative residuals periodogram for subject MND1.

Figure 4.12 Normalized cumulative residuals periodogram for subject MYO1.

Figure 4.15 Sample and AR power spectra for subject MYO1.

Figure 4.16 AR power spectra of subjects NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 obtained from twenty MUAPs recorded from the biceps brachii muscle.

Figure 4.17 Histograms of duration, spike duration, and amplitude for the NOR, MND, and MYO subjects. Median, SIQR, and percentage of polyphasic MUAPs are given for each group (crossed bars show polyphasic MUAPs).

Chapter 5

DISCUSSION

5.1 Material

In this study, data was given from the Department of Neurophysiology of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics. Forty subjects were involved in this study, 12 NOR, 15 MND, and 13 MYO. These subjects have undergone a routine electrodiagnostic examination of peripheral nerves and skeletal muscle. Diagnostic criteria for the subjects selected were based on clinical opinion, biochemical data, and muscle biopsy. Only subjects with no history or signs of neuromuscular disorders were included in the normal group. Furthermore, the biceps brachii muscle was examined because it is a proximal muscle of the shoulder girdle that is usually affected at an early stage in both MND and MYO. Also, its easy accessibility has made it attractive to study and widely reported in the literature.

5.2 Hardware setup

The electrical characteristics of the amplifier, the analog to digital converter (A/D), the filters, as well as the sweep time and the sampling frequency are very important in the EMG data acquisition. In this part, the hardware parameters used will be given and discussed with those suggested in the literature.

5.2.1 Amplifier and A/D converter

The noise level of the Medelec Mystro preamplifier used in this study, is typically less than $5\mu\text{V}$ peak to peak ($0.8\mu\text{V}$ rms) at 1Hz to 10kHz bandwidth with shorted input. The thermal noise level contribution of the needle electrode is $2\mu\text{V}$ rms, thus increasing the total noise level to about $10\mu\text{V}$ peak to peak (Buchthal, 1973). In addition, the quantization noise level of the A/D converter contributes to the total noise level. The quantization noise is given as $q/\sqrt{12}$, where q is the quantization step. For $2\mu\text{V}$ quantization step the quantization noise level is $2\mu\text{V}/\sqrt{12} = 0,6\mu\text{V}$, or approximately $2\mu\text{V}$ peak to peak. Thus, the total noise level is about $12\mu\text{V}$.

EMG was acquired with a 12 bit A/D converter. This gives ± 2048 quantisation levels, with ± 2048 and $\pm 4096\mu\text{V}$ ranges for 1, and $2\mu\text{V}$ quantization steps respectively. Mostly, EMG was recorded in the $\pm 2048\mu\text{V}$ range and to a less extend in the $\pm 4096\mu\text{V}$ range. The use of a 12 bit A/D converter was suggested by Stalberg et al (1986). A 12 bit A/D converter was also utilized in several EMG studies (Graupe et al, 1978, 1983., Doerschuk et al, 1983., Hefftner and Jaros, 1988;

Pfeiffer and Kunze, 1993).

5.2.2 Filters

To avoid distortion in MUAPs shape, the filter settings should be set at 2Hz to 10kHz (Buchthal and Rosenfalck, 1955; Guld et al, 1970). The same filter settings were also suggested in a variety of EMG studies (Vitasalo and Komi, 1974; Hefftner and Jaros, 1988; Pfeiffer and Kunze, 1993).

5.2.3 Sweep time and sampling frequency

A sweep time of 50ms and a sampling frequency of 20kHz were used. The sampling frequency selected should be high enough so as to ensure proper capture of the EMG signal. Stalberg et al (1986) suggested that normal MUAPs are adequately sampled at 10kHz, but sampling rates up to 20kHz might be required for MUAPs with very short rise time. Pfeiffer and Kunze (1993) who carried out MUAP frequency analysis used a 10kHz sampling rate.

5.3 Recording procedure

It is of paramount importance that a significant number of individual potentials are statistically evaluated. It has been shown by Buchthal (1957) that at least 20 MUAPs must be recorded from different sites in a muscle in order to get representative values which can be compared with the normal values. This criterion was also followed in this study.

5.4 The Parametric pattern recognition method

In manual quantitative MUAP analysis (Buchthal, 1954a) only MUAPs that are repeated three times in the EMG acquisition were selected for analysis. The method was liable to give biased results. On the other hand, automatic identification and selection methods do not intervene, or rely their results on one's intuition. In this work the EMG was analysed using the PPR algorithm (Pattichis, 1992).

The PPR algorithm was designed to identify three MUAPs that belonged to the same group. The classification was based on the MUAP features: number of phases, amplitude, spike duration, and duration examined in sequence.

5.5 MUAP set extraction

As it was mentioned above the PPR algorithm tries to identify at least three MUAPs that belong to the same group based on certain criteria. A group of three or more MUAPs forms a set. MUAPs belonging to a set were averaged to obtain an averaged MUAP envelope. The averaged MUAP envelope was referred in this work as MUAP. Each MUAP consisted of 512 data points

(25,6ms) with its maximum peak in the region of 200 points (10ms). MUAPs were required to have their maximum positive peak occurring approximately at the same point otherwise the results of spectral analysis would be biased. MUAPs were acquired with a 20kHz sampling rate. Sampling rate was reduced to 10kHz by rejecting every other point in the MUAP data sequence so as to reduce computation time without loss of information (Stalberg et al, 1986). The mean was subtracted from each MUAP because failure to do so may result in distorted or biased spectral estimates (Marple, 1987).

5.6 FFT spectral estimation

Each MUAP was passed through a Hamming window to reduce the sidelobes effect in the spectral estimate. Sidelobes need to be suppressed in order to reveal the presence of weak signal components that may be present in the spectrum. Marple (1987), in a window performance study, suggested the Hamming window among rectangular, triangular, Hann, Nuttall, Gaussian, and equiripple windows. Bilodeau et al (1990, 1991, 1992) as well as Pfeiffer and Kunze (1993) used a Hamming window in their EMG studies. Zero padding was also applied to each MUAP data sequence prior to spectral estimation. Zero padding was also used by Basmajian et al (1985). It should be noted that the zero augmented sequence does not enhance frequency resolution. The benefits are a smoother power spectrum and a more accurate determination of the frequencies of the various spectral components. The resolution of the power spectrum is approximately the reciprocal of the MUAP data sequence observation interval which is $1/NT$, where $T = 100\mu\text{s}$ is the sampling interval. For 256 data points the maximum possible resolution in the power spectra is $1/(256 * 0,0001) \approx 39\text{Hz}$. By zero padding the data sequence to 1024 points, frequency components are interpolated between every 39Hz, at approximately every 10Hz. Finally, the sample spectrum of each MUAP was computed by applying the FFT. The FFT spectra were plotted together with the AR spectra and will be discussed later in this chapter.

5.7 AR modeling

5.7.1 AR model

Parametric models achieve better PSD estimators, higher spectral resolution, and avoid spectral leakage effects present in the non-parametric or classical spectral estimation techniques. Parametric models of random processes include the autoregressive (AR) model, the moving average model (MA), and the autoregressive moving average (ARMA) model. The selection of one of the three models requires some a priori knowledge concerning the spectral shape of the process investigated. The AR model is appropriate for spectra with sharp peaks and no deep nulls. The MA model is suitable for spectra with deep nulls but no sharp peaks. Finally, the ARMA model can represent both kinds of extremes. The computational burden to estimate the AR

parameters is often significantly less than that required to estimate the MA or ARMA parameters. Thus, the AR model is the most popular, even though it may not be the model of least parameters. Better estimation statistics are usually possible if the number of parameters to be estimated is minimized (Box and Jenkins, 1976).

AR modeling has been widely used in both surface and needle EMG studies. Particularly, AR modeling has been investigated for the control of prostheses (Graupe and Cline, 1975; Graupe et al, 1978; Sherif et al, 1981; Doerschuk et al, 1983; Triolo et al, 1988; Triolo and Moskowitz, 1989), for the control of functional electrical stimulation (Graupe et al, 1988; Hefftner et al, 1988), in muscle fatigue studies (Kim and Lee, 1990; Kihwan and Minamitani 1990; Zhou et al, 1990), for surface EMG diagnostic studies (Inbar and Noujaim, 1984; Lucas et al, 1986; Paiss and Inbar, 1987; Mulavara et al, 1993), and for needle EMG diagnostic studies (Coatrieux, 1983; Maranzana et al, 1984; Basmajian et al, 1985; Elia et al, 1992, 1993, 1994).

5.7.2 *Stationarity*

AR modeling requires that the EMG signal fitted be stationary over the given interval. This implies that the signal statistics do not change in that interval. The stationarity of the surface EMG signal has been investigated by a number of researchers (Inbar and Noujaim, 1984; Hefftner, 1986; Popivanov and Todorov, 1986). Findings demonstrated weak stationarity of the SEMG signal for intervals shorter than 1,0s using the run test.

Inbar and Noujaim (1984) divided the EMG signal into segments of 0,5, 1,0, 2,0 and 4,0s analysed into epochs of 32ms. Mean square values were computed from these intervals and analysed with the run test (Bendat and Piersol, 1971). It was found that for the biceps brachii EMG signal, sampled at 1kHz, the 1,0s intervals were always stationary, whereas intervals of 2,0s and larger were not. Hefftner, 1986 also used the run test to demonstrate weak stationarity over short time intervals. Popivanov and Todorov (1986) also confirmed weak stationarity of SEMG recorded from the biceps brachii and abductor digiti quinti muscles between intervals of 60 to 1000ms. The stationarity of means and dispersions was checked for various EMG segments using the run test.

In this work each MUAP of 256 data points was divided into 16 intervals, and the stationarity was checked by their mean and standard deviation values using both the run and the reverse arrangements tests. In the reverse arrangements test, each sequence of 16 mean and standard deviation values was tested at a significance level of $\alpha = 0,05$. The hypothesis that the data are stationary would be accepted if each sequence of 16 measurements produced a reverse arrangements value in the region $38 < A \leq 81$. In the run test, the mean $\bar{x}_i$ and standard deviation, s_i

of each segment i ($i=1, 2, \dots, 16$) were checked against their median value computed from all 16 intervals. The number of sign changes present in each sequence determined the observed number of runs. The accepted region of runs for stationarity is $4 < r \leq 13$ at a level significance of $\alpha=0,05$.

The results of the stationarity test for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups are shown in Tables 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7 respectively. The percentage of MUAPs in each subject studied that passed the stationarity test using both the $\bar{x}$ and s statistics are tabulated. Findings demonstrated that MUAPs analysed by their mean and standard deviation values were generally stationary over the acquired length.

In the case of $\bar{x}$ statistic, both the run and reverse arrangements tests performed equally well in all disease subjects. In the case of the NOR group 92 percent of MUAPs passed the run test, and 96 percent passed the reverse arrangements test at a significance level of $\alpha=0,05$. The MND and MYO groups gave similar results. 92% of MUAPs in the run test and 97% of MUAPs in the reverse arrangements test satisfied the requirements of the $\bar{x}$ statistic test for stationarity in the MND group. Finally, in the case of MYO group MUAPs were found to be stationary with a success rate of 89% and 86% in the run and reverse arrangements tests respectively.

When the stationarity of MUAPs was checked with the s statistic, it was found that the reverse arrangements test performed better compared to the run test. In the case of the NOR group, 75% of MUAPs satisfied the run test, whereas 87% of MUAPs fulfilled the requirements of the reverse arrangements method. 65% of MUAPs in the run test and 81% of MUAPs in the reverse arrangements method were given to be stationary in the case of the MND group. In the MYO group 82% and 90% of MUAPs satisfied the run test and reverse arrangements test respectively. Results also showed that a higher percentage of MUAPs passed the stationarity test when analysed by their mean rather than by their standard deviation values using both the run and the reverse arrangements tests.

5.7.3 Model order selection

In various EMG studies, optimal model orders in the range of 3 to 20 were reported using different selection criteria. Graupe and Cline (1975), in their study for functional electrical stimulation discrimination of various EMG signals, used the AIC, the residuals autocorrelation function, and the variance of the prediction error to compare differences between the AR coefficients computed from large order models and lower order models. They found that the

prediction error was already white for a model order of three, and that coefficients of such an order were very close to the coefficients of much larger order models. Doerschuk et al (1983), studied the EMG upper extremity limb function discrimination. They reported that AIC did not show a minimum for orders up to 20 whereas the portmanteau statistic of the residuals did not increase for orders larger than 4. Findings suggested that the AIC overestimated the model order. Paiss and Inbar (1987) found that 2 to 7 parameters were needed to model the SEMG acquired from the biceps brachii muscle. The AIC criterion and the linear prediction error variance were used to determine the model order p . Triolo et al (1988) suggested that an AR model of order four was adequate to model EMG of the posterior lateral thigh at different contraction levels, electrode positions, and limb functions. The AR model order selection was based on diagnostics performed on the residuals. Inbar and Noujaim (1984) used the normalized error test as well as the residual signal to find the optimum model order. AR modeling was applied on SEMG recorded from the biceps brachii muscle at 50% of maximum voluntary contraction. It was found that a model order of 20 was required for EMG segments of 500ms long. Coatrieux (1983) reported that the AIC suggested the use of model orders 6 to 7 and 14 to 15 for surface EMG recording and 7 to 9 and 11 to 13 for needle EMG recording depending on the force of contraction. Maranzana et al (1984) used the FPE, AIC, and the MDL criteria for the AR model order selection and the Anderson and the portmanteau test statistic for checking the whiteness of the residuals of simulated needle EMG signals. AR models of order 1 to 9 were proposed. Basmajian et al (1985) also suggested an AR model of order 6 in a needle EMG study.

In this work the FPE, AIC, and MDL criteria were used for the selection of model order. The normalized residual energy was computed for each of the above criteria. Tables 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10 show the optimal model orders and the normalized residual energies for the FPE, AIC, and MDL criteria of each subject examined from the NOR, MND, and MYO groups respectively. The FPE and AIC criteria gave identical results. Both the FPE and AIC selection criterion functions were minimized at the same model order. Thus, the resulting normalized residual energies were exactly equal. This was somehow expected, since the AIC and FPE criteria give asymptotically equivalent results as N tends to infinitive (Marple, 1987). The model orders determined by the AIC were higher in all subjects of all disease groups compared to the MDL criterion. The AIC and MDL criteria gave orders in the range 5,25 to 8,00 and 3,55 to 4,60 respectively for the NOR group. In the case of the MND group, optimal model orders ranged from 5,15 to 10,40 and from 3,65 to 6,20 for the AIC and MDL criteria respectively. Optimal model orders for the MYO group varied from 3,65 to 7,55 and 2,95 to 5,60 for the AIC and MDL criteria respectively. Mean values of order p were 6,083 for AIC and 4, 117 for MDL for the NOR group. The MND group gave mean order values of 7,670 and 4,747 for the AIC and MDL criteria respectively. Finally,

in the case of the MYO group averaged values of p were 5,985 and 4,185 for the AIC and MDL criteria respectively. Model orders obtained with the MDL criterion were reduced by 32% for the NOR group, 38% for the MND group, and 30% for the MYO group compared to the AIC criterion. The above results are found to be in agreement with previous findings (Kashyap, 1980; Elia et al, 1993) that reported that the AIC tends to overestimate the model order. The lower or similar normalized residual energy for the AIC criterion was in general lower when compared to the normalized residual energy obtained with the MDL criterion. This was expected, since higher model orders reduce further the linear prediction error value. The AIC criterion was subsequently used in the estimation of MUAPs AR spectra though the MDL criterion could have been used as well.

Plots displaying the linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$ and the AIC criterion against model order p for each MUAP of the NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects are shown in Figures 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6 respectively. From the above plots, it may be observed that AIC criterion decreases as model order increases. This continues until the AIC criterion function reaches its minimum. The model order corresponding to the minimum value of AIC is called the optimum model order. As model order is allowed to increase further, the AIC starts increasing again.

Similarly, $\hat{\rho}_p$ is decreasing at the beginning with increasing model order like the AIC. This continues until a certain model order is reached above which $\hat{\rho}_p$ reduces monotonically. This suggests that the linear prediction error alone cannot be used for the selection of the model order. Thus, the model order obtained with the AIC criterion can be considered a reasonable selection. In a number of cases though both the AIC and $\hat{\rho}_p$ tracked exactly or very nearly the same model order. Also, in a limited number of cases, $\hat{\rho}_p$ was varying irregularly above a certain model order with more than one minimum points occurring on the same plot.

5.7.4 Modified covariance method

The AR parameters can be estimated using both block and sequential data algorithms. The Yule-Walker, the Burg, the covariance, and the recursive least square (RLS) algorithms were mainly the algorithms used in the various EMG studies. For the control of prosthesis the sequential least squares algorithm was basically adopted due to its fastest possible convergence rate and higher accuracy in the AR parameter estimates (Graupe and Cline, 1975; Graupe et al, 1978, 1983; Doerschuk et al, 1983; Hefftner et al, 1988; Hefftner and Jaros, 1988). In a muscle fatigue study, Paiss and Inbar (1987) used both the autocorrelation and the covariance methods. They found that the variance of the AR parameters was smaller in the covariance method than in the

autocorrelation method. In applications investigating the diagnostic usefulness of EMG, Coatrieux (1983) used both the Yule-Walker and the Burg methods. Maranzana et al (1984) also used the Yule-Walker method and the recursive least square (RLS) algorithm at the initial stage of their work. Finally, the RLS method was adopted because of its convenience. In this work the modified covariance method was used because it eliminates the drawbacks present in the rest block data algorithms like spectral leakage, frequency bias, and line splitting (Marple, 1987). Block data algorithms include the Yule-Walker, the Burg, the covariance, and the modified covariance methods. The Yule-Walker method suffers the most degradation in resolution of all methods due to the windowing effects present in this method (Marple, 1987). Also, the Burg and the Yule-Walker methods suffer from line splitting.

This means that two or more closely spaced peaks can occur in the spectral estimate. The modified covariance spectrum, based on the same data as in the other two methods, yields a single peak at the correct frequency (Fougere et al, 1976). Several problems associated with the Burg method, including spectral line splitting and bias of the frequency estimate, appear to be eliminated when the modified covariance method is used. Also, the computational effort of the modified covariance method is comparable with the Burg algorithm. For $p \ll N$, the modified covariance algorithm is actually more efficient than the Burg algorithm when the same order is used for both algorithms (Marple, 1987).

5.7.5 *AR model validity*

Once a model has been identified and the parameters estimated, diagnostic checks must be applied to the model to determine its adequacy. These checks are customarily applied to the residuals of the model. The residual is the error between the actual signal and the signal predicted by the model. The model will be adequate only if the model error is white noise. The order of the model must so be chosen to guarantee that the residual is nearly white noise.

A first step in this checking process is a visual inspection of the residuals. Such plots are given in Figures 4.7, 4.8, and 4.9 for the NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. These plots show that the spectrum is flat or slightly varying. Residuals periodograms resembling the spectrum of a white noise sequence verify the adequacy of the AR model. The model fitness can also be checked by the normalized residuals cumulative periodogram. For a white noise process the plot should be a straight line passing through the origin having a slope equal to 2. Figures 4.10, 4.11, and 4.12 give the normalized residuals periodograms for the NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. All plots yielded almost a straight line with a slope of two through the origin. Deviations from this line are justified in Box and Jenkins book (1976). Results

showed that all model orders selected gave white noise residuals.

A quantitative measure of the amount of whiteness of the residuals signal can be obtained by the portmanteau test statistic. Results of the portmanteau test statistic of the residuals are given in Tables 4.11, 4.12, and 4.13 for the NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. The Q statistic is calculated for each MUAP, and its value is then compared to the value $\chi_{\alpha, \nu}^2$ taken from the chi-square distribution curve. α is the level of significance, and ν is the number of degrees of freedom. α is taken as 0,05 in this work. ν is equal to $(m-p)$ degrees of freedom. The Q statistic reduces the degrees of freedom in the chi-square distribution by the number of the estimated model coefficients p . The hypothesis of model adequacy is accepted if Q is smaller than $\chi_{\alpha, \nu}^2$. From the results obtained, it is obvious that Q is much smaller than $\chi_{\alpha, \nu}^2$ indicating that the model is adequately represented in all cases.

5.8 AR spectral estimation

5.8.1 AR spectrum

The AR spectrum of each MUAP is computed from the identified AR parameters. Zero values were also added to the AR coefficients sequence prior to AR spectral estimation so as to extrapolate more power points at a more dense set of frequencies (Basmajian et al, 1985; Marple, 1987). Zero padding gives a smoother power spectral density, removes ambiguities present in the non zero augmented power spectrum, and estimates frequencies of the spectral components more accurately.

Power plots of the AR spectrum are given only for three subjects one from each disease group. These are shown in Figures 4.13, 4.14, and 4.15 for the NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects respectively. The FFT spectrum is also given in the above spectral curves for comparison. The MUAPs of the above referred subjects are illustrated in Figures 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3 respectively. Power spectral curves showed that AR and FFT spectra were in very good agreement. Generally, the AR spectra either followed closely the FFT spectra or formed the envelope of their partner particularly when the latter were spiky. Power curves also showed that AR spectra approached further the FFT spectra of spiky character at increasing model orders. Similar results were also reported in needle EMG studies using AR modeling (Coatrieux, 1983; Maranzana et al, 1984; Basmajian et al, 1985; Elia et al, 1992, 1993).

5.8.2 AR spectral measures

In this work various power and frequency parameters were derived from the AR spectra and given

in Tables 4.14 to 4.19. Power parameters computed were the following: power levels at 100, 200, 300, 500, 750, 1000, 1250, 1500, 2000, and 2500Hz and moments of order 0, 1, and 2. Frequency measures extracted from the AR spectra were the following: centre frequency, median frequency, peak power frequency, upper and lower cut-off frequencies, bandwidth, quality factor, and frequencies at power levels of -5, -10, -15, -20, and -25dB. Frequency and power measures were calculated for each subject studied by averaging the frequency and power values of individual MUAPs.

In the case of the MYO group all frequency parameters are higher and of larger power compared to the normal group. Results show that the power spectrum in the case of myopathies is shifted towards higher frequencies as expected. This was also reported in a number of studies (Richardson, 1951; Walton, 1952; Fex and Krakau, 1957; Gersten et al, 1965; Kopec and Hausmanowa-Petrusewicz, 1966; Carlsson et al, 1972; Sandstedt, 1981; Elia et al, 1993). On the contrary, frequency components in the case of the MND group are lower and of smaller power compared to the normal group. This suggests that the power spectrum in the case of MND is shifted towards lower frequencies as anticipated. Also, Figure 16 which shows the AR power spectra of NOR1, MND1, and MYO1 subjects averaged over twenty MUAPs clearly indicates the displacement of MND and MYO power spectra towards lower and higher frequencies respectively compared to NOR power spectrum. This was also verified in a number of studies (Kaiser and Petersen, 1963, 1965; Gersten et al, 1965; Kopec and Hausmanowa-Petrusewicz, 1966; Larsson, 1975; Herberts et al, 1973; Shigiya et al, 1973; Sandstedt, 1981; Elia et al 1993).

Spectral Moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 in the myopathy group were also found to be higher than the normal group. M_0 actually represents average power in the spectra. Since the power of all frequency components in the MYO group were higher than the NOR group, it follows that M_0 would be higher too. This is also justified by the mean power frequency. Centre frequency is the frequency which corresponds to the mean power of the spectrum. Since the power of the CF in the MYO group is higher than the respective value in the NOR group, it follows that M_0 in the MYO group is higher too compared to normal. Following a similar approach, it may be justified that M_0 in the MND group is lower than M_0 in the NOR group. Spectral moments M_1 and M_2 represent the area of the power spectra after being multiplied with frequency raised to power one and two respectively. Thus, since all frequency components in the MYO group were of greater value and of higher power compared to the NOR group, it follows that M_1 and M_2 in the MYO group would be higher than in the NOR group. A similar interpretation of the results can be given for M_1 and M_2 of the MND group compared to the NOR group. The above findings are also confirmed by histograms of moments M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups

which are shown in Figure 4.19.

5.9 AR coefficients, model order p , and linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$

Group statistics of model order p , linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$, and AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} , are provided in Tables 4.20, 4.21, and 4.22 for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups respectively.

Results showed that higher model orders were needed for the MND subjects compared to the NOR subjects due to the higher complexity in shape. This is also confirmed by histograms of model order p for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups in Figure 4.18. MUAPs from subject MND1 are displayed in Figure 4.2. MND MUAPs are characterised by longer duration, higher amplitude, and greater number of phases compared to NOR MUAPs. Histograms of duration, spike duration, and amplitude in Figure 4.17 strongly support the above. The polyphasic potentials constituted 23% of all MUAPs recorded from the MND group compared to 3% in the NOR group. On the contrary, lower model orders were obtained in the MYO group compared to the NOR group due to the simple form of MUAPs in the MYO group. This is also illustrated in Figure 4.18 which shows histograms of model order p for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups. MUAPs recorded from subject MYO1 are given in Figure 4.3. These are characterised by shorter duration, smaller amplitude, and lower number of phases, compared to MUAPs recorded from the NOR group. This is also shown in Figure 4.17 which gives the histograms of MUAP duration, spike duration, and amplitude of the NOR, MND, and MYO groups. The incidence of polyphasic potentials is 6% in the MYO group, whereas the percentage of polyphasic potentials in the NOR group is only 3%. Findings above were also confirmed in a MUAP AR spectral analysis study carried out by Elia et al, 1993.

Mean and standard deviation values of model order p were $6,08 \pm 3,01$ for the NOR group, $7,67 \pm 4,19$ for the MND group, and $5,98 \pm 3,28$ for the MYO group. The results above clearly indicated that twelve AR coefficients were adequate to represent MUAP data in all disease groups. Model order p was also included in the feature selection analysis to evaluate its diagnostic performance.

Linear prediction error variance $\hat{\rho}_p$ was expected to decrease at higher model orders. This was not very clear from both the statistics of individual subjects and the group statistics. Also, the standard deviation of $\hat{\rho}_p$ was large compared to its mean in all disease groups. The above suggested that $\hat{\rho}_p$ cannot be used for discriminating muscle pathology since no definitive

conclusions can be drawn from its statistics.

5.10 Cepstral coefficients

Twelve cepstral coefficients were determined directly from the estimated AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} . Their group statistics for the NOR, MND, and MYO groups are given in Tables 4.23, 4.24, and 4.25 respectively. The classification performance of cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 and c_1 to c_{12} was examined by doing cluster analysis. The motivation of using cepstral coefficients as diagnostic features in this study is due to their higher identification accuracy in speech recognition compared to AR coefficients (Atal, 1976). Cepstral coefficients were also found to be better discriminators than AR spectral parameters and AR coefficients in a MUAP feature selection study carried out by Elia et al, 1994.

5.11 Statistical analysis

5.11.1 Univariate statistical analysis

Univariate analysis was carried out on various selected time and AR spectral parameters. Parameters included were the following: i) time parameters duration, spike duration, amplitude, and number of turns, ii) frequency parameters centre frequency, median frequency, peak power frequency, bandwidth, quality factor, and spectral moments of order 0,1, and 2, and iii) model order p . Results are given in Table 4.26. As shown in Table 4.26, the hypothesis that parameters means are equal is rejected at a significance level of 5 percent for all parameters. t-test analysis was also carried out between NOR-MND, NOR-MYO, and MND-MYO groups. In NOR-MND group, there was no significant difference in peak power frequency. Additionally, amplitude and model order p in NOR-MYO group and quality factor in MND-MYO group were not significantly different.

5.11.2 Multivariate statistical analysis

Correlation analysis was carried out to establish the interrelationship between various selected time and AR spectral parameters. Correlation analysis was performed on the features described in section above. Table 4.27 shows the correlation matrix of various selected parameters from 12 normal, 15 MND, and 13 myopathy subjects. The total number of MUAPs included in the analysis were 800. Results in Table 4.27 showed that there was no strong correlation between time parameters and between time parameters and the remaining selected features. Moments M_0 , M_1 , M_2 , CF , $FMED$, and BW were highly correlated. Peak power frequency F_0 was found to be moderately correlated with the above parameters. Quality factor and model order were not highly

correlated between each other or with the remaining features.

Correlation analysis was also carried out between power and frequency parameters but results are not presented here. It was found that most of the power parameters P_{100} , P_{200} , P_{300} , P_{500} , P_{750} , P_{1000} , P_{1250} , P_{1500} , P_{2000} , and P_{2500} and the frequency parameters F_1 , F_2 , F_5 , F_{10} , F_{15} , F_{20} , and F_{25} were moderately to highly correlated with spectral moments M_0 , M_1 , M_2 , CF , $FMED$, F_0 , and BW and were eventually considered as redundant.

Highly correlated features were excluded from the final feature set. Finally, features that were included in the feature selection analysis study were the following: i) duration, spike duration, and amplitude, ii) median frequency, quality factor, and moment M_2 , and iii) model order p . Turns was not strongly correlated with anyone of the features involved in the correlation analysis, but it was left out so as to have a reasonable number of features in the time parameters feature set. On the other hand, moment M_2 though highly correlated with median frequency was included in the final group of features of the AR spectral parameters set.

5.12 Feature selection analysis

Univariate and multivariate analysis

Features included in the feature selection analysis were the following: i) Dur, SpDur, and Amp, ii) $FMED$, Q , and M_2 , and iii) p . Results are listed in Table 4.28. Results showed that duration is the best classifier among time parameters. $FMED$ is the best feature among AR spectral parameters. Finally, model order p was ranked among the poorest classification features in the univariate analysis, whereas the multiple covariance analysis classified it third among all features studied.

5.13 Cluster analysis

5.13.1 *K-means nearest neighbour classifier*

Cluster analysis was carried out for the following group of features: i) AR coefficients α_1 to α_5 , ii) AR coefficients α_1 to α_{12} , iii) cepstral coefficient c_1 to c_5 , iv) cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} , v) model order p , vi) AR spectral parameters M_0 , M_1 , M_2 , CF , $FMED$, F_0 , BW , and Q , and vii) time parameters Dur, SpDur, Ph, and Amp. Standardised data was used in the K-means cluster analysis. Results of the K-means nearest neighbour classifier are given in Table 4.29.

The time parameters feature set gave the highest classification performance among all feature sets both for the training and the evaluation sets. Their diagnostic yield was the highest in the training

set (67% CCs) and was improved further in the evaluation set (81% CCs). Model order p gave the next highest diagnostic yield in the training set with 63% CCs. However, its diagnostic yield was reduced to 56% in the evaluation set. The cepstral coefficients were shown to be better discriminators than the AR spectral parameters and AR coefficients for the training set. However, the cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 , AR spectral parameters, and AR coefficients α_1 to α_5 gave exactly identical results in the evaluation set with 44% CCs. Furthermore, AR parameters α_1 to α_{12} and cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} in the evaluation set gave the poorest diagnostic yield.

5.13.2 *Euclidean distance classifier*

The Euclidean distance classifier evaluated the same group of feature sets as described above in the K-means cluster analysis for both the training and evaluation sets. Standardised data was also used in this analysis. Results obtained with the Euclidean distance classifier are given in Table 4.30. The time domain parameters gave the best diagnostic yield for the training set with 92% CCs. Conversely, their diagnostic yield for the evaluation set was equal to 50%. The AR spectral parameters, the cepstral coefficients, and the AR coefficients followed the time parameters feature set in this sequence in both the training and evaluations sets.

Chapter 6

CONCLUSIONS

6.1 Conclusions

In this study AR spectral analysis has been proposed as a diagnostic tool for discriminating MUAPs recorded from normal subjects and patients suffering with Motor Neuron Disease and myopathy. Autoregressive modeling was implemented in two stages. First, the EMG signal was processed in the time domain. MUAPs were recorded, extracted, measured, and classified into sets. Then, MUAPs were analysed in the frequency domain. MUAPs were fed to an AR model whose coefficients were computed using the modified covariance method. The model order p was computed using the Akaike information criterion. The fitness of the model was tested by performing diagnostic checks on the residuals. MUAP parameters derived from the AR power spectra as well as from the AR and cepstral coefficients were then used as diagnostic features. Their classification performance was also checked and compared to time domain parameters. The classification performance of the selected features was evaluated using feature selection and cluster analysis methods.

The duration measure was found to be the best discriminator and the median frequency as the second best feature in the univariate analysis method. On the contrary, the multivariate analysis method gave the median frequency as the best discriminator, followed by the duration parameter. Model order p was ranked among the poorest features in the univariate analysis, whereas the multiple covariance analysis classified it third.

The K-means nearest neighbour cluster analysis results showed that the time parameters feature set which includes duration, spike duration, phases, and amplitude gave the highest diagnostic yield. The number of CCs for this model was 67% in the training set and 81% for the evaluation set. The AR spectral parameters, cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 , and AR coefficients α_1 to α_5 gave similar results for the K-means cluster analysis in the region of 42 to 46% CCs. The diagnostic performance of the above models was slightly increased or decreased for the evaluation set compared to the training set.

The Euclidean distance classifier gave the time domain features set with the highest classification yield, followed by the AR spectral measures and the cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_5 . The AR spectral measures gave 71% CCs for the training set and 75% for the evaluation set. The cepstral

coefficients c_1 to c_3 gave 67% and 69% *CCs* for the training and evaluation sets respectively.

In conclusion MUAP AR spectral modeling, combined with time domain analysis provide useful information in the quantitative assessment of neuromuscular disorders.

6.2 Future work

Future work will investigate the application of artificial neural network models for the classification of MUAP data extracted in this work. The main objective of artificial neural network systems is to achieve human like performance, if possible in the pattern recognition and classification tasks, such as in speech and image processing and analysis. The advantages of artificial neural networks that make them so attractive to investigate are the following: i) exhibit adaptation or learning abilities, ii) pursue multiple hypothesis in parallel, iii) may be fault tolerant, iv) may process degraded or incomplete data, v) make no assumptions about underlying data probability density functions, and vi) seek answers by carrying out transformations (Rumelhart et al, 1986). Preliminary findings of neural network models excited separately with the AR spectral measures, AR coefficients, and cepstral coefficients have shown better classification performance than both the K means nearest neighbour classifier and the Euclidean distance classifier. Further work is currently in progress.

Recently, an integrated diagnostic system for assessing certain neuromuscular disorders was developed based on artificial neural networks (Schizas et al, 1994). The diagnostic system is composed of modules that independently provide numerical data to the system from the clinical examination of a patient, and from various laboratory tests from histopathology, neurophysiology, biochemistry, genetics, and molecular genetics that are performed. The examination procedure has been standardized by developing protocols for each specialized area, in cooperation with experts in the area. At the conclusion of the clinical examination and laboratory tests, data in the form of numerical vector represent a medical examination snapshot of the subject. Artificial neural network (ANN) models were developed using the unsupervised self organizing feature maps algorithms. The system was tested with data collected from 71 subjects suffering with various forms of neuromuscular disorders. The ANN models were trained with the data from 41 subjects and tested with the data from the remaining 30 subjects. The diagnostic yield that was obtained for the unknown cases was in the region of 73 to 93%. Laboratory tests of neurophysiological data used in the above system are limited to EMG findings in the time domain only. MUAP AR modeling spectral analysis findings from this study can be included in the existing protocols in an effort to enhance the diagnostic performance of the system, as well as to provide a more complete description of the biological processes investigated.

Furthermore, wavelet analysis, a new method of analysing the time and frequency contents of signals (Chui, 1992) may be applied in MUAP analysis. The wavelet transform is used to describe signal information distributed over time and frequency. By capturing signal information which is locally distributed in time-frequency windows, signals can be represented with less storage. In addition, signals often contain most of their information only in a small number of time-frequency windows. Thus, by representing the signal, only the wavelet coefficients corresponding to the small number of time-frequency windows must be kept. Preliminary results have shown that wavelet transform, makes possible the decomposition of MUAPs into highly localized time-frequency components that was not possible before (Pattichis and Pattichis, 1993). This decomposition should be further explored to see if it provides additional diagnostic information that may have not been apparent in current MUAP analysis techniques.

APPENDIX 1

ESTIMATION OF AR PARAMETERS USING THE MODIFIED COVARIANCE METHOD

A.1 Introduction

The estimation of the AR model parameters depends on the availability of the autocorrelation sequence of the random process. Usually, the autocorrelation is not known, so an AR spectral estimate must be made from the available data. Various algorithms have been developed in the literature so as to produce estimates of the AR model parameters and in turn evaluate the AR PSD function. Such algorithms are the block data algorithms which operate on a fixed block of data samples and recursively yield higher order AR model parameter estimates based on lower order AR parameter estimates.

Block data algorithms fall into three categories: i) correlation function estimation method, ii) reflection coefficient estimation methods, and iii) least squares linear prediction estimation methods. The Yule-Walker method falls into the first category. The Yule-Walker algorithm produces estimates of the autocorrelation sequence from the available data samples. The estimated autocorrelation sequence is then substituted in the Yule-Walker equations to yield the AR coefficients and from these the AR PSD function. The geometric, the Burg, and the recursive maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) algorithms belong to the second category. These methods provide the AR parameter estimates from reflection coefficient sequence estimates. The third category includes the autocorrelation, the covariance, and the modified covariance methods. The autocorrelation and the covariance methods perform separate minimization of the forward and backward linear prediction squared errors. On the other hand, the modified covariance method performs combined minimization of the forward and backward linear prediction squared errors. In this work the modified covariance method was used since it avoids spectral leakage effects, frequency bias, and line splitting problems associated with the rest block data algorithms (Marple, 1987).

A.2 Modified covariance method

It may be shown (Marple, 1987) that a forward or backward linear predictor can fit an AR process of order p for N available data samples assuming that the prediction error is a whitened process, in which case the linear prediction coefficients can be equated to the AR coefficients. The

forward and backward linear prediction errors may be defined over the range $n=1$ to $n=N+p$, if it is assumed that data prior to the first sample and after the last sample are zero ($x(n)=0$ for $n<1$ and $n>N$).

The modified covariance method minimizes the average of the forward and backward linear prediction squared errors over the available data. The average of forward and backward linear prediction squared errors is given by

$$\rho_p^{fb} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^f(n)|^2 + \sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^b(n)|^2 \right] \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $e_p^f(n)$ and $e_p^b(n)$ are given in equations below

$$e_p^f(n) = x(n) - \hat{x}^f(n) = x(n) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p^f(m) x(n-m) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$e_p^b(n) = x(n-p) - \hat{x}^b(n-p) = x(n-p) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p^b(m) x(n-p+m). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Since the summation range of squared errors in equation (A.1) is the same as that of the covariance method, this combined forward and backward least squares error approach has been called the modified covariance method.

Minimization of equation (A.1) with respect to all prediction coefficients leads to the following set of normal equations:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_p^{fb}}{\partial \alpha_p^{fb}(j)} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_p^{fb}(j)} \left[\sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^f(n)|^2 + \sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^b(n)|^2 \right] \right\} = 0$$

for $j = 1, \dots, p$

$$\text{or} \quad \sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^f(n) x(n-j)| + \sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^b(n) x(n-p+j)| = 0.$$

Equation above simplifies further by substituting the values of $e_p^f(n)$ and $e_p^b(n)$ as given in equations (A.2) and (A.3) respectively, yielding

$$\sum_{n=p+1}^N \left\{ |x(n) x(n-j)| + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) |x(n-m) x(n-j)| \right\} + \sum_{n=p+1}^N \left\{ |x(n-p) x(n-p+j)| + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) |x(n-p+m) x(n-p+j)| \right\} = 0$$

$$\text{or } r_p(0,j) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) r_p(m,j) = 0 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\text{where } r_p(0,j) = \sum_{n=p+1}^N [x(n) x(n-j) + x(n-p) x(n-p+j)] \quad \text{and}$$

$$r_p(m,j) = \sum_{n=p+1}^N [x(n-m) x(n-j) + x(n-p+m) x(n-p+j)].$$

The superscripts f and b have been omitted from the linear prediction coefficients $\alpha_p(m)$ because these apply now to both forward and backward prediction errors.

The resulting least square error is obtained by taking the square of both the forward and backward linear prediction errors over the summation range $n = p+1$ to $n = N$. It can be shown that equations (A.2) and (A.3) reduce to equations (A.5) and (A.6) respectively i.e.,

$$\sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^f(n)|^2 = \sum_{n=p+1}^N x(n) x(n) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) \sum_{n=p+1}^N [x(n) x(n-m)] \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\text{and } \sum_{n=p+1}^N |e_p^b(n)|^2 = \sum_{n=p+1}^N x(n-p) x(n-p) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) \sum_{n=p+1}^N [x(n-p) x(n-p+m)]. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Substituting the two equations above in (A.1)

$$\rho_p^{\text{fb}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=p+1}^N \left\{ [x(n)x(n) + x(n-p)x(n-p)] + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) [x(n)x(n-m) + x(n-p)x(n-p+m)] \right\}$$

$$\text{or } \rho_p^{\text{fb}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[r_p(0,0) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) r_p(0,m) \right]$$

$$\text{or } 2\rho_p^{\text{fb}} = r_p(0,0) + \sum_{m=1}^p \alpha_p(m) r_p(0,m) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\text{where } r_p(0,0) = \sum_{n=p+1}^N [x(n)x(n) + x(n-p)x(n-p)] \quad \text{and}$$

$$r_p(0,m) = \sum_{n=p+1}^N [x(n)x(n-m) + x(n-p)x(n-p+m)].$$

Equations (A.4) and (A.7) lead to the set of normal equations

$$\underline{R}_p \underline{\alpha}_p^{\text{fb}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\rho_p^{\text{fb}} \\ \underline{0}_p \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\text{where } \underline{\alpha}_p^{\text{fb}} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_p(1) \\ \vdots \\ \alpha_p(p) \end{bmatrix}$$

$\underline{0}_p$ is the null vector with p elements

$$\underline{R}_p = \begin{bmatrix} r_p(0,0) & \underline{r}_p^T(0,j) \\ \underline{r}_p(0,j) & \underline{R}_{p-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\underline{R}_{p-1} = \begin{bmatrix} r_p(1,1) & r_p(2,1) & \dots & r_p(p,1) \\ r_p(1,2) & r_p(2,2) & \dots & r_p(p,2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ r_p(1,p) & r_p(2,p) & \dots & r_p(p,p) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$r_p(0,j) = \begin{bmatrix} r_p(0,1) \\ r_p(0,2) \\ \vdots \\ r_p(0,p) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Thus, by solving the set of normal equations given in (A.8) the AR parameter estimates can be calculated using the modified covariance algorithm as given by Marple (1987). The AR power spectrum estimate is then computed by the ARMA subroutine as described in Marple (1987).

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